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**MOBILITY, STABILITY AND
SUSTAINABILITY: CHALLENGES
FOR SOCIAL SCIENCE,
MANAGEMENT, IT AND
EDUCATION**

**EDITORS
Dr. P. S. Aithal
Prof. Pradeep M. D.**

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Paper 1

STUDENT GRADING IN HIGHER EDUCATION FOR COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM

P. S. Aithal¹ & Suresh Kumar P. M.²

¹College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

²Department of Sociology and Social Work, Christ University, Bangalore - 560029, INDIA

E-mail : psaital@gmail.com

Abstract:

Higher Education aims to produce quality professionals who would be economically productive and contribute to the society. Here comes the question how fit are they? Are our passing out graduates ready to take up and perform jobs successfully? Is the present education equipping them for that? What should be the assessment of a graduate be based on? Higher education aims to impart competency to the learners and generally the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired desired level of competence. Examination and assessment are a key indicator for measuring performance of a graduate in the existing credit based education system. The credit based system in higher education is founded on the assumption that grades which a student has secured by way of assessment and evaluation speak what a student has earned by way of education. But the question is how to measure the competency among the graduates who pass out. Various indicators are available in competency based education system (CBES), most important among them is employability. Employability is the capacity to take up and perform job independently with relative ease, although this is something that is usually subject to decision of the employer and therefore difficult to set a bench mark. Our competency measurement model suggests various performance indicators which could directly give a quantifiable idea to judge how successful a person would be in a given job. This paper attempts to outline the major factors contributing to competency, their objectives and outcome. An attempt has also been made to identify such factors which contribute to predict performance in a job situation by judging competency level performance indicators. The interventional strategies for higher education institution is also outlined here.

Keywords : CBES, Competency based education, Outcome based education, Performance level, Competency Measurement model, Competency Measurement Scales.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The higher education has an objective to develop systematic thinking ability of the students by means of enhancing knowledge, skills, and experience which in turn expected to increase the confidence of the solving problems of self and society [1]. In the process of imparting higher education, two models are considered to be relevant in the current century which are (1) Conventional classroom based education model [2-4] and (2) Technology supported online ubiquitous education model [5, 6, 7]. The two higher education systems which are

expected to be attractive to the learners are Choice Based Credit system (CBCS) and Competency based Education system (CBES) [8].

Presently Indian higher education system follows choice based credit system of assessment and evaluation. A credit system is a systematic way of describing an educational programme by attaching credits to its components. The credits in higher education systems may be based on different parameters, such as student workload, learning outcomes and contact hours. University Grants Commission has come up with the Choice Based Credit System (CBCS), a programme in which the students while choosing the prescribed course, which is the core, can opt for any elective or minor or soft skill courses and the entire assessment is graded, based on a credit system. The CBCS provides choice for students to select the elective components in any other institution as well.

Competency-Based Education System (CBES) is a significant improvement in CBCS model. It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment. Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution. A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content [6, 8]. This model allows students to work and learn anywhere and as per the curriculum of the University/Higher education institution where they enrolled for their courses have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is most challenging and there is no hard and fast method as well as the rating scale accepted by universally exists today. Competency based education system is not a new concept and is under discussion since 1970 [10-17]. Due to the limitations involved in the evaluation and distribution of scores/ rating of outcomes, CBES model in higher education could not become popular and not adopted in most of the universities.

2. Objectives of the Paper :

This conceptual paper based on explorative research has the following objectives :

- (1) To analyse the distinctive features of competency based education system CBES.
- (2) To study the factors which contribute to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome.
- (3) To discuss Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages of both CBES and its competency rating scale.
- (4) Challenges in offering CBES as outcome based education system.

3. Features of Competency Based Education System (CBES) :

Competence means ability or capability and performance is the proof of competence. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. As opposed to this, is the credit based system where the grades directly speak what a student has earned through

education?. But the question is how to measure competency among the graduates who want to pass out. However, this is something that is decided by the employer and difficult to set a benchmark at university level during evaluation for offering graduation certificate. In this paper, we have proposed two grading methods based on a modified 1-10 rating scale and the other is a modified Likert scale model to measure and express competency of a graduate in a given subject/area. In its final form, the Likert Scale is a five or seven-point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on the Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged.

CBES involves educating a student in order to improve the competency of performance in one or more fields of specializations. This includes enhancing his knowledge, skills, and experience along with ethical aspects of doing things systematically to the expectations of the industry. The evaluation of competency should focus on developing the progress report of the candidate periodically to report the speed of learning and achieving the different levels of competency. Such an evaluation process and outcome is called competency rating and reporting. The distinctive features of CBES are :

- (1) Competency based education system focus on building and measuring some pre-defined competency in performing a specified task efficiently and effectively.
- (2) It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment.
- (3) Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit.
- (4) It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills, and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution.
- (5) A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content.
- (6) The system allows a student to choose any number of areas where he/she is interested to enhance the skills required to do a particular job with learned required competency.

4. PERFORMANCE LEVEL MEASUREMENT IN CBES :

Competency based education system focus on developing working skills on a particular set of jobs during a time frame. Those working skills together called as competency comprises of wide ranging skills and expertise mixed with attitude conducive to perform the job adequately and satisfactorily. Various teaching-learning methods including classroom teaching, laboratory based learning, experiential learning, experimental learning, online

learning, internship based projects, fieldwork practicum etc. are adopted to realize the goal in competency based education system. These methods are geared to provide the right opportunity to the student to develop these competencies. Major factors that contribute to build the competency has been identified and classified. Our competency measurement model suggests that what counts on employability are a sum total of outcomes achieved through a set of identifiable factors which has clear objectives and verifiable indicators. The following table (Table 1) list out areas of competency, their performance objective and outcome. The performance indicators suggested against each of this give a clear idea on the expected traits required for employability.

Table 1 : Factors which contributes to competency and their expected performance outcome.

Sl. No.	Areas of Competency	Performance Objective	Performance Outcome	Performance Indicator
1	Communication and comprehension	Translating Thoughts	Rapid Action	Speed
2	Proficiency in writing	Transmitting Ideas	Quick response	Accuracy
3	Generation of new ideas	Trying out new and easier ways	Innovation	Productive efficiency
4	Preserving a vision in life	Commitment to goals	Adaptability	Value addition
5	Desire for learning	Improvement in life	Job meaningful	Pro-activeness
6	Attitude towards life	Combine personal ambitions with employment goals	Positive energy	Positive view
7	Respect for fellow-beings	Accept others contribution	Increased co-operation	Receptiveness
8	Self-control	Strength and determination	Courage in action	Accountability
9	Self confidence	Faith in one's own action	Sustained interest	Quality in work
10	Creativity	Ability to make things happen	Gogetter	More output

Various rating scales have been used in the past to measure intangible quantities like attitude, feelings, quantities, perception, love, affection, happiness, pain, satisfaction, status, talent, knowledge, etc. Most popular among them is the Likert Scale [18]. In higher education institutions competency measurement becomes more relevant than credit grading and calls for the need to evolve measurement parameters relevant to the indicators. A modified Likert Scale Model could be used for this purpose (Table 2). This scale or metric supports to measure and express the competency of a graduate in a given area to a greater extent in a very systematic way. This scale is a 10 point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level.

Table 2 : Competency rating model in a given skill based on 1-10 rating scale

Sl. No.	Competency Grading Level	Grade Point
1	Outstanding	10
2	Excellent	9
3	Very good	8
4	Good	7
5	Above Average	6
6	Average	5
7	Below Average	4
8	Weak	3
9	Very Weak	2
10	Extremely Weak	1

5. GRADING IN COMPETENCY BASED SYSTEM :

This could be a useful tool for the employer to predict the success of a new employee when he is admitted into a new job. For the educational institution it is a reference point to sharpen its interventional strategy to build capability in the new pass-out. It is safely presumed that a person who obtains a minimum of 50% in aggregate and separately in each of these 9 components would perform satisfactorily. Higher score is reflective of the merit of the candidate (Table 3).

Table 3 : Measurable parameters for competency assessment

Sl.No.	Performance Outcome	Operational Indicators	Measureable parameters
1	Rapid action	Speed	Follow deadlines
2	Quick response	Accuracy	Fewer mistakes
3	Innovation	Productive efficiency	Better planning
4	Adaptability	Value addition	Exceeding limitations
5	Job meaningful	Pro-activeness	More output
6	Positive energy	Positive views	Demonstrate initiative
7	Increased cooperation	Receptiveness	Maintaining enthusiasm
8	Courage in action	Accountability	Readiness to follow directions
9	Sustained interest	Self-motivation	Appropriate actions
10	Ability to make things happen	Gogetter	Turns challenges into opportunities

6. MODELS FOR COMPETENCY GRADING SYSTEM :

6.1 Model 1 for Competency Reporting:

This model is based in 1-10 rating scale. This is an extension of choice based credit system grading. Here, the competency level of a student under evaluation is graded using grade points anywhere between one to ten. Absent to evaluation process by the respective student is graded as zero. Depending on evaluator’s assessment on a candidate, grading level and corresponding grading point should be determined. Table 3 lists various competency levels and the corresponding grade points.

6.2 Model 2 for Competency Reporting:

Even if competency is an intangible property, it can be measurable to some extent through various traits. To measure the competency of a graduate in any area/field, we propose another model which is a modified Likert scale model. This scale or metric supports to measure and express the competency of a graduate in a given subject/area to a greater extent in a systematic way. In its final form, this scale is a seven point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on this modified Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged. This model is based on 7 point Likert Scale. Here, seven grades are allotted based on a student’s competency on a given skill or subject. The evaluator, through demonstration, shall decide the competency level and fix it to any deserved level and the grade points should be allotted accordingly. In this model, the competency reporting system may follow either optimistic assessment by using positive scale, a most likely assessment scale called neutral scale, or a pessimistic assessment model by using negative scale.

(1) Positive Scale :

This is an optimistic /positive assessment scale used to measure and report the strength of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(2) Neutral Scale :

This is a neutral most-likely assessment scale used to measure and report the abilities of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(3) Negative Scale :

This is a negative assessment scale used to measure and report the weakness of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

6.3 Complete Performance Measurement Model based on above Scales :

The competency based performance measurement format consists of listing of various skills required to perform a job satisfactorily and the competency grading level of a candidate along with corresponding grade point. This also includes the time taken by the candidate to reach the required competent level as shown in Competency Report format given in table 4. An example of competency report format shown in table 4 based on positive scale for Accounting job is shown in table 5.

Table 5 : Example of competency report based on positive scale for Accounting job

Name : Ashok B.		Roll No. : 2019K29		DOB:04/04'1999
S.No.	Skills Required for the Job	Competency Grading level	Grade Point	Time taken to reach the level
1	Knowledge	Very good	5	12 months
2	Working skills	Good	4	18 months
3	Expertise level	Excellent	6	12 months
4	Communication	Average	2	08 months
5	Proficiency in writing	Very good	5	18 months
6	Generation of new ideas	Excellent	6	18 months
7	Preserving a vision in life	Average	2	24 months
8	Desire for learning and improvement in life	Excellent	6	12 months

9	Attitude towards life	Average	2	18 months
10	Respect for fellow-beings	Below Average	1	18 months
11	Self-control	Good	4	12 months

7. ABCD OF CBES AND ITS RATING SCALE :

Out of many analysis frameworks developed to analyse a system, concept, ideas, models, or strategies, ABCD analysis framework is an effective and simple framework which analyse the usage of the system/model, factors affecting the system/model, and deep insight into the system/model through identifying critical constitutional elements (elemental analysis) [19-22]. The variation in ABCD analysis called ABCD listing is a qualitative discussion method. ABCD listing consists of listing of advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the usage of the system/model [23-39]. In this section, the advantages, benefits, constraints, and Disadvantages of CBES and its rating system developed are listed :

7.1 Advantages :

- (1) CBES focus on building and measuring some pre-defined competency for a student in performing a specified task efficiently and effectively.
- (2) CBES provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment.
- (3) CBES allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit.
- (4) In this system, a student can progress in his own pace, while improving knowledge, skills, and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution.
- (5) In CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content.
- (6) In CBES, a student can choose any number of subjects where he/she is interested to enhance the skills required to do a particular job with learned required competency.

7.2. Benefits :

- (1) The competency of a student is measured in some quantifiable terms.
- (2) The competency scores provided by this evaluation system gives idea to the employers to judge the capability of a graduate while appointing for a job.
- (3) Since CBES provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education, the students can pursue their education in their own plan & pace.
- (4) CBES provides an opportunity to the learner to continue his education while working for a job.
- (5) Based on scored academic credit, a students’ knowledge and skills in doing a particular job can be determined.
- (6) CBES system and its evaluation model do not allow promoting unemployable graduate.
- (7) CBES system allows a student to take any number of subjects so that one can differentiate himself in academic process along with opportunity to become multi-subject specialist.

7.3 Constraints :

- (1) CBES implementation constraints
- (2) CBES Evaluation timeframe constraints
- (3) CBES curriculum constraints
- (4) Lifelong Continuous improvements required based on environmental changes
- (5) Educators mental block for changing the CBCS to CBES

7.4 Disadvantages :

- (1) Since CBES is mainly skill based education system and hence students are deprived to acquire to general education related to a special area.
- (2) The CBES model is focussed model so that the advantages of STEM/STEAM models are not incorporated.
- (3) Student is allowed to become expert on one or related area in order to get required level of competency so that he may become obsolete soon due to changes in environmental conditions like change in technology.
- (4) Adopting new system and training faculty members for new evaluation system is difficult.

8. CHALLENGES OF MEASURING COMPETENCY OF GRADUATES USING ABOVE MODEL :

Based on the proposed model one can measure the skill levels of a student on positive or negative grading scale. Some of the challenges CBES while implementing and evaluation are as follows :

- (1) The competency level in a specific skill for a job can be represented by offering an appropriate grade and corresponding score by the University evaluator so that it can be considered in industry while offering the job.
- (2) The model based on one to ten levels of competency looks straight forward but there are many implementation constraints for the evaluators as well as the industry job interviewers.
- (3) The process of evaluation of competency in a given skill or in an identified job needs experts in that job. Hence the evaluator's team should comprise of both academicians and industry experts. This makes customization of even evaluation process which leads to complex and time consuming process.
- (4) CBES is suitable for honours degrees both in under-graduation (UG) and post-graduation (PG) levels to measure the additional skills imparted during the training period where as it is not practical for pass degrees in UG and PG levels of higher education.
- (5) This model is more suitable for further studies for continuous of education while working in industries instead of students of formal continuous education system.

9. CONCLUSION :

Competency-Based Education System (CBES) is a significant improvement in CBCS model due to the fact that it provides an opportunity to customize and personalize the learning process. CBES in higher education provides a proper direction of required skills to be developed by a student while choosing the subjects, and the assessment. Competency-based education programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. In this system, students have to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience. CBES is a continuous improvement program for individuals and as per the demands of the industry. Since a student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses, but to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content. Hence the model allows students to work and learn anywhere and have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is discussed in this paper and an appropriate solution of grading model based on developed competency is proposed.

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Paper 2

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH SELF HELP GROUPS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANGALORE TALUK

Harinakshi¹ & Mithun Chandra R. K.²

¹Faculty, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: harinakshisuvarna02@gmail.com

²Faculty, Department of Business Management, University Evening College, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: mithoonchandra008@gmail.com

Abstract:

India, our country, is well known for its cultural heritage, civilization, religion and its geographical features. We proudly portray our nation as “Bharat-Mata” and raise slogans in praise of our unity, integrity and dignity. While doing so, we fail to realise that “Bharat-Mata” means mother to every Indian. But in India, women are considered weak compared to men. Right from the beginning women were considered as knowledge-less creatures, which were kept inside the kitchen to do all the household chores. She was never allowed to indulge in social and political affairs of the society. But today, the status of women is at a high level not only in the family but also in the business area compared to men. Women, today, are not only confined to domestic chores like upbringing of children but they also form an integral part of the society and make a significant contribution to the development of the nation. Primarily, now women are dominant as much as men they become equal to men in every area. Thanks to universal declaration of human rights to receive inheritance, divorce or express themselves liberally. Secondly, when we look at the business field, we see the profile of working, producing women today. They also gained dignity in the business area today. It is possible to see women in every field just because of the women empowerment programme. This research is undertaken to learn about the women empowerment program conducted by the Self-Help Groups and to know how they benefit women members socially and economically.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Self-Help Groups, Members & Financial Support.

1. INTRODUCTION

India, our nation, is well-known for its cultural heritage, economy, religion and geographical characteristics. We are proud to depict our country as “Bharat-Mata” and raise slogans to praise our unity, honour and dignity. In doing so, we fail to realise that for every Indian, “Bharat-Mata” means mother. But in India, compared to men, women are considered weak. From the beginning, women were treated as knowledge-less beings that were kept in the kitchen to do all the household chores. She was never allowed to participate in society’s social and political affairs. Yet today, not only in the home, but also in the business area, women’s status is high compared to men. Women today are not only confined to domestic tasks such as children upbringing, they are also an integral part of society and make a significant contribution

to the nation's growth. First and foremost, women are now as dominant as men in every field as they become equal to men. Thanks to universal human rights declaration to obtain property, divorce and express themselves in a progressive manner. Second, we see the profile of employed, creating women today, as we look at the field of business. They have also earned credibility in today's business environment. Only because of women's empowerment program can women be seen in any field.

2. WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Essentially, this creates an environment in the simplest terms in which women can make independent decisions about their personal development and shine as partners in society. According to Swami Vivekananda, "There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved. It is not possible for a bird, to fly on one wing". It the 1985 International Women's Conference in Nairobi, which described women's empowerment as a philosophy, it was presented as a redistribution of social power and control of resources for women. Women Empowerment in India, therefore, aims primarily to enhance their social functioning through a quantitative and qualitative change, especially in the field of education, health and employment.

3. SELF-HELP GROUPS

Self-Help Organisations are informal voluntary networks of people from the same socio-economic background to solve their common problems. Methods followed by Self-Help Groups to Empower the Women:

- To sensitise target area women for the end of the self-help group and their importance in their empowerment process
- To build group feeling between them
- Boost women's innovative decision-making
- Provide them with appropriate training on how to manage their business, how to use the funds raised in self-help groups, how to use their loans for productive purposes.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has been designed with the following objectives-

- To study the operating system of Self-Help Groups for the mobilization, delivery and management of funds.
- To know the women empowerment programme conducted by the Self-Help Groups.
- To evaluate economic and social benefits obtained by members since entering SHGs.
- To measure the satisfaction level of the beneficiaries of Self-Help Groups.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study undertaken includes both primary and secondary data. The primary data is first-hand information collected for the purpose of survey. The information for this study is collected through questionnaire. The structured questionnaire was distributed to respondents in Mangalore Taluk. The secondary data is obtained from various journals, books, magazines and a few web sites. The data collected through the questionnaire was put together in the form of tables and analysed, simple percentage method is used for the analysis.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Majority of respondents (i.e.,60%) were joined SHG for the reason of availing loan & remaining 40% were joined to save money. As per my study all the respondents were satisfied

by joining SHG. Out of 50 respondents' only 32 respondents' availed loan provided by SHG. Among them 17 respondents (i.e., 53%) were availed loan for domestic expenditure & remaining 15 respondents (i.e., 47%) were availed loan for Self-Employment (like textile shop, sole trading concern, etc). Out of 32 respondents 11 respondents (i.e., 35%) were availed a loan of below Rs. 10000, 17 respondents (i.e., 53%) were availed loan between Rs.10000-25000, 2 respondents (i.e., 6%) were availed loan of Rs.26000-50000 & remaining 2 respondents (i.e.,6%) were availed more than Rs.50000. The study reveals that 100% of respondents agreed that they get loan at low rate of interest in SHG. 100% of respondents were became financially empowered after joining SHG. The study concerned that financial status of women empowered after becoming member of SHG. Out of 50 respondents 46% respondents were undergone training given by SHG& remaining 54% were not undergone any form of training. Training was about establishing their own business, tailoring classes, etc. Out of 50 respondents 64% were responded that they are getting social recognition, very much after joining SHG & remaining 36% were not getting that much social recognition.

7. FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

Most of the respondents joining SHG for availing loan. In study region, maximum number of respondents availed loan amount of Rs.10000-Rs.25000. All the respondents opinion is that loan is given at low rate of interest. All the respondents become financially independent after joining SHG. Majority of respondents getting social recognition after joining SHG and they gained confidence in doing their work on their own after joining SHG. The bank should advance adequate credit to the SHG members according to their needs. The office bearers managing the group should be given nominal financial benefits, which will enable them to be more involved in the activities of the group. It is suggested that training on innovative economic activities by using the resources in & around the taluk may be given to the members. The incentives may be given for prompt repayment of loan. This will draw the attention of the groups to repay the loan.

8. CONCLUSION

The modern era has created many obstacles that have put many nations experiencing change, transcending their tradition and culture. New issues must be tackled in order to bring about our nation's social and economic development. Women's empowerment by self-help groups is the most significant one. SHG has undeniably started to make a significant contribution to alleviating poverty and empowering the vulnerable, particularly women in rural areas. Women are the vital infrastructure and their inclusion will accelerate the speed of social development. The sure way to contribute to economic growth and social development is to invest in women's skills and inspire them to achieve choices and opportunities. The atmosphere of rural women not only leads to helping different groups of women and children, but also to help the facilities and community as a whole. This research is an effort to examine member's socio-economic development and women's success in SHG. SHG's performance has been great. As a member of SHG, the lower numbers of women are positively affected. Women's involvement in this scheme is discovering inner and building capability. If the above suggestions are made by the relevant authorities, the study will further improve the status of women in the Mangalore taluk.

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Paper 3
**MOBILITY, STABILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN
BANKING AREA**

Dr. C. K. Hebbar

Research Professor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Mob: 9448351299, hebbarkc@yahoo.com

Abstract

The present era of industrialization and globalization has added a lot of comforts and luxuries to human life. Through this banking also become a so easier task. Mobile banking is a new trend in modern banking era which allows it's user to perform banking transactions without visiting to the bank as well as without usage of any physical currency. Stability refers to that banks provide effective services their customers, a sound system and procedures govern the banking system, have ability to pay their customers and have ability to absorb risks. It is very important for banks to be pro-active and increase the rate of the growth of the economy. Banks should apply morality of sustainability and responsibility to their business model. It should formulates strategy for their products and services.

Keywords: Mobility, Stability, Sustainability, Mobile Banking, Challenges.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is the most complicated issue the world is facing today. Environmentalism is wide way of thinking idea's and social change regarding involvement for environmental protection for effective state of environment. In response to the present discourse of progress that over exploits our nature for economic prosperity. To measure & mitigate the risk of climate change caused by human activity, there have been continuous endeavors across the globe. Sustainability is the key issue. Due to global warming, the rapid change in climate have direct impact on our bio-diversity, agriculture, forestry water resources & human health. To mitigate climate change, many countries have made commitment necessary. There is a need to promote certain measure for sustainable development and corporate social responsibility. Green movement for protection of environment has brought about a change in the way. Mobile banking plays a pivotal role in protecting environment with the aim of creating good social activities. It is a technique of reducing of carbon emissions and improves financial assistance to green technology and making pollution free environment. It is a way of accelerating the growth and development of the economy by influencing on the financial world. It reduces the paperwork by introducing eco-friendly system that is usage of electronic media instead of paper transaction. Mobile banking plays a prominent role in the protection of natural resources.

2. OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY

This study aims to know the concept of Mobility, Stability and sustainability in banking area, to study the transformation of mobile banking, to study the different challenges of mobile banking and to identify the Difference between Stability And Sustainability in Banking. This paper reviews the literature on the basis of secondary data collected from various sources such as articles, research papers, annual reports, sustainable reports,

company's official website etc. for analyzing the Mobility, Stability and sustainability in banking area.

3. MOBILITY IN BANKING

Among all the industries where technology has become a defining factor and is taking the industry by storm, the banking industry is facing a hurricane. Among all the technologies that are shaking up the banking world, the one that is bringing in the most significant transformations across the board is mobility. The banks on the other hand, are working hard to ensure that customers can manage and take care of their banking transactions on any mobile device, whenever they want, from anywhere in the world. The introduction of mobility in the banking sector has erased the traditional methods of working and brought about a great change in the working style that the industry has been used to. It has helped banks stay connected with the world besides speeding up the process. Mobility is helping banks to meet customer expectations, increase employee productivity and cut down on the cost of day to day transactions carried out manually. With mobility the transaction process is automated without any human participation. Customers are getting familiar and comfortable with undertaking basic financial services on their mobile devices.

4. TRANSFORMATIONS THAT HAVE RESULTED DUE TO MOBILITY IN THE BANKING.

Bank employees working processes have moved on to smart phones and tablets replacing personal computers. All banks and financial institutions have advanced websites and mobile apps for customers to carry out their financial transactions and other processes through their mobile devices. Banks work together with app development companies to constantly upgrade their mobile apps to enable customers to manage their bank accounts globally, from any location they are in. With Mobile banking, customers can get any information about the bank's financial services in detail. With multiple security checks at every step, customers are assured of performing more secure transactions through mobile and web apps. Today, banks not only use mobile devices and applications as a channel to offer services to customers but also use it as a tool to connect within the organizations, empower their workforce and control its various processes and assets. So, we not only see basic banking operations performed through mobile devices and applications but also see increased use of mobility solutions within the organizations in complex operations like asset management services, loan approval processes and database management.

5. CHALLENGES

There are multiple challenges facing the banks as they move on to leverage mobility solutions. There is a massive proliferation of devices differing in form, Platform Scalability functionalities and features. The challenge will be to come-up with a solution that fits all. While the world may have been stepping into 5th generation of internet connectivity, still bandwidth latency and coverage is an area of concern if mBanking has Integration Key & Challenges Customer to truly stand to its promise of anywhere, anytime Deployment Experience banking. Security of banking transaction over the Model air is another complicated challenge which calls for continuous intervention as the technology Data evolves. Decision makers should also need to keep Security an eye on the scalability and reliability of mobile & Fraud infrastructure as the usage grows and mobile Detection devices become the major channel from yet- another-channel of contact between customers and the branch. Mobility today is transforming banking services in a big way. It is providing a whole new experience with a huge benefit over traditional banking while making customers lives easier, while empowering and encouraging them to actively participate in their financial lives.

6. STABILITY IN BANKING

Stability refers to that banks provide effective services their customers, a sound system and procedures govern the banking system , have ability to pay their customers and have ability to absorb risks.) The global financial crisis of 2007 was one of the shocking economic disasters of the last one hundred years. Large numbers of banks in the advanced countries were failed causing irreparable damage to the financial system and to the real economy. Central banks learned that banks have to be well regulated

and well capitalised so that they can withstand any crisis. The financial crisis thus provided a valuable lesson to the western countries who boasted that they always have the sophisticated economic system. After the crisis, they introduced a large number of policies for the banking system including strong regulations that were unprecedented in history for them. Failure of banks leaves long scars on the economy as a whole. A bank failure is the failure trust, which cannot be rebuilt. Hence financial institutions should be kept stable and healthy. After the crisis, central banks across the world are strengthening measures like regulation and supervision to keep the banking system stable. Most central banks including the RBI have added financial stability as a core objective of monetary policy. The concept of financial stability or the situation where banks remains healthy, without any weaknesses, became an important priority for central banks after the crisis.

7. WHAT IS FINANCIAL STABILITY?

Financial stability means financial institutions individually and collectively are being able to deliver their functions properly, withstanding external shocks and avoiding internal weaknesses. 'India Financial Stability Report' published by the Reserve Bank of India (March 2010), defines financial stability: "From a macro prudential perspective, financial stability could be defined as a situation in which the financial sector provides critical services to the real economy without any discontinuity.". During the time of the global financial crisis, RBI has made many unconventional measures to protect the banking system. Liquidity support was provided abundantly so that no banks should face stress. The RBI since 2010 is publishing *India Financial Stability Report* to assess financial stability scenario in the country. Financial stability is now one of the three important objectives of monetary policy besides price stability and credit support. In its monetary policy statement in May 2008, the RBI mentioned that sometimes, the objective of financial stability becomes more important than the objective of price stability. A stable financial system is capable of efficiently allocating resources, assessing and managing financial risks, maintaining employment levels close to the economy's natural rate, and eliminating relative price movements of real or financial assets that will affect monetary stability or employment levels. A financial system is in a range of stability when it dissipates financial imbalances that arise endogenously or as a result of significant adverse and unforeseen events. In stability, the system will absorb the shocks primarily via self-corrective mechanisms, preventing adverse events from having a disruptive effect on the real economy or on other financial systems. Financial stability is paramount for economic growth, as most transactions in the real economy are made through the financial system. The true value of financial stability is best illustrated in its absence, in periods of financial instability. During these periods, banks are reluctant to finance profitable projects, asset prices deviate excessively from their intrinsic values, and payments may not arrive on time. Major instability can lead to bank runs, hyperinflation, or a stock market crash. It can severely shake confidence in the financial and economic system.

8. SUSTAINABILITY IN BANKING

The integration of sustainability into the banking sector has taken two key directions. The pursuit of environmental and social responsibility in a bank's operations through environmental initiatives (such as recycling programs or improvements in energy efficiency)

and socially responsible initiatives (such as support for cultural events, improved human resource practices and charitable donations). The integration of sustainability into a bank's core businesses through the integration of environmental and social considerations into product design, mission policy and strategies. Examples include the integration of environmental criteria into lending and investment strategy, and the development of new products that provide environmental businesses with easier access to capital. The second of these categories has the potential to influence business on a larger scale. By integrating sustainability into a bank's business strategy and decision-making processes, institutions can support environmentally or socially responsible projects, innovative technologies and sustainable enterprises. While banks play a crucial role in promoting sustainable development, the industry got off to a late start in acknowledging sustainability as an item on its agenda. In the 1990s, however, it started to play a more active role in sustainable development. The major shift happened when bankers realized poor environmental performance on the part of their clients represented a threat to their business success. The interdependency between a bank's profitability and the environmental record of its clients has influenced the business strategy of both banks and their corporate clients. This has happened in several ways. In particular, to decrease their exposure to environmental liability and to improve risk management, bankers started to look more closely at the environmental performance of their clients. They developed mechanisms to assess the environmental risk exposure of their customers, and to protect themselves from potential losses. This growing concern about clients' environmental performance, manifested in lending and investments decisions, began to act as an additional driver of sustainability in the private sector. Companies were given one more reason to pursue environmentally and socially sound solutions.

9. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN STABILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN BANKING

Stability is a short term snapshot of the banking system - it has the required capital to withstand loss, and is able to payback its depositors as and when claimed - that is being solvent, has liquidity and adequately capitalised. Sustainability on the other hand is a long term phenomenon - that the system would survive all economic and financial impacts, (due to the above stability factors) as well as its capacity to rise from the ashes, may be because of group strength, internally generated surpluses, good corporate governance and probably not being too aggressive in doing banking business and assuming risks.

10. CONCLUSION

It is not the strongest of the species that survive nor the most intelligent, but the one most responsive to change. Since changes are going on anyway, the great thing is to learn enough about them, so that we will be able to lay hold of them and turn them in the direction of our desires. Conditions and events are neither to be fled from nor passively acquiesced in they are to be utilized and directed.

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Paper 4

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS OF LESSONS FROM SOME ANIMALS LIVING BEHAVIOUR

Dr. K.V. M. Varambally* & Dr. P. S. Aithal **

*Research Professor, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University,
Mangalore- 575 001, India

E-mail: kvmvarambally@gmail.com

**Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore - 575001

Email : psaithal@gamil.com

Abstract:

Business organizations need to improve their performance continuously by constantly monitoring their internal and external environment. Organizational improvement is an important issue at any point of time in society and needs different types of behavioural attributes to be followed by managers and the employees to be followed to satisfy or to make an impact on stakeholders. The management thinkers of many schools of thought suggest to find out optimum behaviour to ensure success. It is observed that some Animals in their living style adopt certain behaviour which is in built in their way of survival. The principles behind their living methods have several managerial implications. This paper is based on the living behaviour of animals and the managerial lessons involved in it which are relevant to Business Managers in their business operations.

Keywords : Management lessons, Resilience development, Learning from animals, Learning from reflections.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Learning makes the man better and improves his style of functioning and performance. Continuity in the learning process keeps a man fit in a changing environment. He can exhibit his good qualities and can act as a role model to others in his learning process. A learner cannot only improve himself but also facilitate others to improve their learning in a community. The general perception is that real learning happens at school. A person achieves his learning progression at different levels viz primary, secondary, higher secondary and at under-graduation and post-graduation levels. Teacher plays a key role in shaping the career progression of a student. Teachers at different levels act as mentors, guides, and facilitators of the learning process. However, it is the known fact that the learning process has different dimensions. Apart from classroom teaching learning environment, a student can equip himself better through reading, interaction with others, observation of others performances, associations with learned people and his own reflections. A student keeps himself open to all this avenue can shape himself better and lay a solid foundation to build up his career.

Observation of nature provides learning opportunities for the students and the purpose of this paper is to provide learning avenues to students especially management students from

observing the animals and their living behaviour. Animals follow their own discipline to survive in an open environment. The basic input is taken from Chanakya Neeti Darpana for further elaboration of the paper [1-3]. As per Chanakya's view, there is one learning lesson each from lion and crane, the living style of cock provides four lessons, crow provides five lessons, dog provides six lessons, and donkey provides three lessons. "Simhad Eakam, Bakad Eakam, Shiksha Chatvari Kakkutat Vayasat, Pancha Shikshechha, Shat Sunah Thrinee Gardabaha".

2. OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY :

The very objective of the paper is to draw managerial lessons from the living style of animals such as lion, crane, dog, crow, cock, and donkey. The living behaviour of animals has been taken from Chankey Neethi Darpana written by a well-known expert who wrote famous "Artha Shastra" in about **3000 BC** which provides lessons to govern the country in a systematic way. The principles adopted by animals have been highlighted in the paper which is relevant to Business Managers in the present context. Many management thinkers also studied animal and bird's behaviour and their implications for management and leadership behaviour [4-8].

3. MANAGEMENT LESSONS FROM SOME ANIMALS :

3.1 LESSON FROM LION :

Lion is called the king of the forest. Before executing its work, lion plans properly with adequate care. Once the planning is done it executes with full focus and by synergising its efforts. It won't relax until the work is over. A manager who is in the helm of affairs of business projects needs to understand the concept of planning with care and execution of the project with full thrust. Most of the failures in business happen either due to lack of adequate planning and preparation or execution of the project with wholehearted efforts. The success in business comes to those who dare and act. It seldom comes to timid. Therefore, business managers before venturing into any new projects or business activity need to equip themselves fully with facts and figures, proper analysis of the market condition, and execute the project putting wholehearted efforts. Anything done in a hurry or done without a proper understanding of the market environment may not fetch expected results. The concept of concern and care is very much essential to drive the project in the path of success.

3.2. LESSON FROM CRANE :

Crane when it sights an object like fish, concentrate along with regulating the body and wait for the right time with patience. At right time it catches the object with the right force. Before striking its object, crane calculates the right distance and force required to complete the task. Self awareness, self regulation, self motivation and action at the right time with the right force are the lessons a business manager can learn from the way of living of crane.

A manager needs to focus his attention on the task along with awareness of his strengths and limitations. He needs to evaluate the risk involved, maintain professionalism and take decision at the right time with the right effort. Right decision at right time fetches desirable results. Undivided attention on the problem allows a manager to understand it better and enable him to solve it in a proper way.

3.3. LESSON FROM COCK :

The cock imparts four lessons viz. Early rising, keep ready for self-protection or attacking, allow others to take their due share, and grab its legitimate share. In the early morning, it is a cock which gives the wake up call. Early rising provides flexibility in time so that there will not be any hurry or tension in the day's activity. Time management is very much essential for business managers. This not only shows self-discipline but also enables one to do the duty without much stress or tension. Work without much stress enables a business manager to take planned decisions systematically. His style of functioning can be an example to others for better management.

The second lesson from cock is to keep yourself ready to face challenges. It may be self protection or exhibit required aggression for survival. Keep oneself fit in the changing environment is the need of the hour for business managers.

The third lesson is giving the due share to others. Cock allows others to take their share without any constraints. This quality is essential for managers in employee relationships and employee treatment. Business managers from the point of view of business development need to take care of their employees with an attractive incentive package. Then only they can build the team and lay a solid foundation for business.

The fourth lesson is grabbing its own share. What is the legitimate share should be identified and has to be claimed without any hesitation. A business manager should not have any inhibitions to claim its right remuneration and incentives appropriate to his efforts and risk involvement.

3.4. LESSON FROM CROW :

The lessons from crow are - to be alert and watchful, collect the desirable things for later use, make love in privacy, don't get scared away easily, and don't trust anyone fully.

Alertness and watchfulness are necessary for managers to monitor the business process in the formal framework. It helps to overcome the internal limitations and identify the poor performers. Watchfulness also helps to avoid failures and internal sluggishness.

Resource conservation is required for a business to maintain steadiness in business operations. It enables Business Managers to maintain resilience during the depression and unfavourable situations.

Love is a personal matter which has to be done in privacy to maintain one's dignity and self-respect. Creation of a scene in public brings down the image both of the individual and also the business organisation. From the point of view of the image of the organisation, business leaders need to keep themselves away from scandals and licentious behaviour.

Running a business calls for adequate courage and confidence. If a manager is weak minded, he cannot exhibit his stability and gain employee confidence in the organisations.

Trusting fully or dependent on another person in total may create problematic situations. Watching and testing is a strategic option a business manager needs to maintain to safeguard

his business activity. A person may command terms or deceive the organisation if the organisation is dependent on him fully.

3.5 LESSON FROM DOG :

Loyalty to the master, contented sleep, ready to wake up even for a slight noise, fight ferociously without any shy, eat adequate food when available, not worried if sufficient food is not available are the six qualities of a dog.

These qualities provide guiding principles to a business manager. He needs to exhibit his concern and care with at most loyalty to his organisation. He has to keep himself ready for any tuff work related to his organisation. He needs to have full satisfaction for whatsoever he is getting and has to grab the opportunity for his benefit when available to him. Dissatisfaction or disappointment is common in any work environment. If one is worried too much about this, he cannot put effort for future endeavours. What had happened in the past should not be kept in mind throughout. This constraint his future progress.

3.6 LESSON FROM DONKEY :

Donkey's living behaviour provides three lessons, never refuse to work, have contentedness and stoicity. Donkey works in cold or hot environment. It does tiresome work without complaints and it keeps cool and contented. A business manager has to maintain balance during tuff times as well as a good time. He should know how to manage disappointment and maintain continuity of the business.

4. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS & SUGGESTIONS :

The role of business managers is to make proper decisions for the survival and growth of a business organisation. Proper planning and coordination, motivation and control are necessary to keep up the fitness of the organisation. While taking decisions business managers have to evaluate each and every option for the optimal solution. The lessons from the life behaviour of animals would help the business manager to take the right decisions at the right time.

Wholehearted efforts with proper planning full attention at work, exploitation of right opportunity, develop the team spirit, assertiveness, balancing the good and bad situations, self awareness, self regulation, self motivation, time planning, good relationship, employee care, and concern would help business managers to drive the business towards better heights.

5. CONCLUSION :

A business manager would enable to enrout the business in the path of success by incorporating the above-mentioned lessons which he can learn from the living behaviour of animals. This approach enables him to strengthen the business and also shows others the proper way in business survival and growth.

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Paper 5

STUDY ON MILLENNIAL PERCEPTION ON MARKETING INNOVATION

Veena Rai¹, Pooja Shetty A.² & Kavyashree³

¹Research Scholar, MBA Department, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Mangalore, Karnataka.

Email: veenasanthoshrai@gmail.com

²Second Year MBA, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Mangalore, Karnataka.

Email: poojashetty5009@gmail.com

³ Second Year MBA, Srinivas institute of technology Mangalore Karnataka.

Email: kavyashree651997@gmail.com

Abstract:

This paper deals with the study on the impact of Digital Marketing towards Millennial people who born age between 1981 to 1999. The objective of the study is to analyse how Millennial Use Digital Media, how much and the reason for using digital media. The paper gives about the role of youths in the Digital Industry. It basically explains how important is digital Marketing and helps it's changing the company's marketing strategies. The reason for conducting this study is to observe various marketing strategies that are used in Digital Media and determine which ones are preferred by Millennial and are effective in influencing their perception and behaviour. This study has 104 Millennial responses are used on Digital Media daily in their life, more importantly, this study highlights millennial view web site frequently write online product review that people will see Digital Ads rarely for Millennial do not like pop up ads and they like Visuals in websites and actual grabbing attention of products or services.

Keywords: Digital marketing: Internet, Digital media, millennial, Digital industry, Perception.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital Marketing or E-Marketing refers to the use of marketing techniques through Digital Media or Internet like social media, websites, blogs etc. With increasing usage of digital marketing consumers and companies can able to reach their targets easily. It is all about the targeted, measurable, and interactive marketing of end products or services with the use of digital technologies and media to reach and transfer leads into clients and retain them[1]. Millennial has been identified as a driving force behaving digital media and online shopping. Millennial or Gen Y people's unusual attraction both Academic and Managers works. Gen Y people are called as first-generation people who use Digital Media or Internet for the purpose of getting information or to buy products[2].

2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Study on Millennial Perception and Behaviour regarding Digital Marketing/Digital Media with special reference to Stream LL Bengaluru”.

3 NEED FOR THE STUDY

Using digital advertising and marketing or net advertising and marketing is very crucial for any enterprise. These youths will affect deeply on the market because of the regular use of Digital Medias.[3]

4 LITERATURE REVIEW

J Järvinen, H Karjaluoto - Industrial Marketing Management, (2015). This study explains the performance of the companies by using Web analytics. The main purpose of this study to measure literature and use web analytics. This offers companies to measure Digital Marketing performance. The study shows that organizations efforts to use marketing metrics system and the resulting outcome cannot be understood without seeing the processing of metrics data and use of the system. should update their capabilities and also use current or modern Digital Marketing Techniques.

5 OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY

To Analyse the Millennial Perception towards Digital Marketing to know their view about digital media, online marketing, online shopping, and promotional activity with Digital Marketing[4][8] To Analyse the Millennial Behaviour towards Digital Marketing, Digital Media, online shopping and ads. For this study methodology adopted the data interview of primary data gathering. The source of secondary data collection is from books, websites, and journals

6. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Figure No. 1.1 Response on Role of Website Design

Role of Website Design in Digital Marketing	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Disagree	2	2
Moderate Disagree	8	8
No opinion	27	26
Moderate agree	24	23
Agree	43	41
Total	104	100

Table no 1.1 clearly state that Majority that is 41% of respondents agree to this statement

Figure No. 1.2 Responses regarding knowledge of Digital Marketing

Knowledge regarding Digital Marketing	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	103	99
No	1	1
Total	104	100

Table no.1.2 clearly state that 99% of respondents are having knowledge about Digital Marketing.

Figure No. 1.3 Response regarding interest in learning Digital Marketing

Regarding interest in learning Digital Marketing	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	8	9
Maybe in Future	59	57
Already know about the concepts	5	5
Not Interested	31	29
Total	104	100

Table no 1.3 this clearly state that 9% of respondents have interest, 57% of respondents thought to learn in future, 5% of respondents already know about Digital Marketing, 29% of respondents no interest in learning digital marketing

Table No. 1.4 Response regarding information is needed before joining any Digital Marketingcourse

Information about Digital Marketing course	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	55	52
Agree	39	37
Disagree	1	1
Strong disagree	10	10
Total	104	100

Table No. 1.4 clearly state majority that is 52% of respondents strongly agree to this statement, 37% of respondents agree with the statement, 10% of respondents strongly disagree to the statement, 1% of respondent disagree to the statement

Figure No. 1.5 Response regarding the familiarity with Digital Marketing Techniques

Digital Marketing Techniques	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SEO	3	3
SEM	5	5
Social Media marketing	66	62
E-mail Marketing	11	11
Pay-per-click advertising (PPC)	3	3

Content marketing	3	3
All the above	5	5
None of above	8	8
Total	104	100

Table no 1.5 reveals that majority that is 62% of respondents are familiar with Social Media Marketing

7. FINDINGS

- Majority of the respondents believe that by using web site design it is easy to get information about the products.
- Majority of the respondents agree that Digital Marketing is going to replace Traditional Marketing.
- The study clearly shows that all the respondents heard about Digital Marketing.
- By analysing the above study most of the respondents heard about Digital Marketing through social media
- 59% of the respondents were interested to learn digital marketing in future and 9% were really interested to learn immediately
- From the above study majority of the respondents agree that they need much information about Digital Marketing.
- By analysing data from the study majority of the respondents agree that, there is great Job opportunity for Millennial to Digital Marketing Industry.
- Majority of the respondents moderately agree that choice of Digital Marketing is best for the future job option.

8. SUGGESTIONS

- Web site design is the main attraction in Digital Marketing but most the people pay less attention to that so more attention in website design has to be done.
- Strategic Promotion of Digital Marketing is the need of the day.
- Good website for Digital Marketing with information regarding the concepts and techniques and online course, queries etc.
- More and more pop up ads will disturb to viewers.
- By providing online course facility people may come to learn Digital Marketing.
- Encouraging Millennial to study digital marketing is the need of the day

9. CONCLUSION

In future India with the use of digital marketing has tremendous growth in the national income and it helps many start-ups to grow their business in a big way. The internet penetration rate in India has increased to the greatest extent. And also the small or medium level business can get a very good benefit from the Digital Marketing [6]. Usage of internet by maximum number of people in the country would help in the development of the business in the country and there will be more demand for the domestic products as well [5]. Since all most all young and adults of the world are having connection with web it would be very easy for the marketers to target the customers making it cost effective, as traditional marketing is taken over Digital marketing.

importance should be given to the growth of digital marketing concentrating on Millennial by analysing their perception and expectation as they can be involved in making digital marketing much more effective therefore, Younger generation should be encouraged to take up digital marketing as a job opportunity and create awareness among them is the need of the day[11,12].

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Paper 6
**STUDY ON SOFT SKILL TRAINING AND
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME FOR MANAGEMENT
STUDENTS**

Sagar Srinivas
Srinivas University
Pandeshwara mangalore-01
Email _sagarsrinivas@ymail.com

Abstract:

The higher education in India as well as the market scenario and requirement is changing very fast and moving ahead due to stiff competition. A decade ago, those individuals who had a brilliant academic record with added work experience were well sought after by most of the corporate institutions with a fixed range of pay as remuneration. But today hard skills and experience are not sufficient enough for the way in and growth in the corporate world. Employers prefer to hire and promote those persons who are resourceful, ethical, and self directed and motivated with good communication and soft skills. Shortage of soft skills in the candidates has resulted in low hiring by corporate. Corporate giants have also made its point clear regarding soft skills training programme to be included in the management courses and will surely have a positive overall development in the course.

In spite of such immense significance of soft skills, many management colleges are hesitant to incorporate soft skills training in the curriculum of management courses. This paper is based on the improvement training and development programme has on the students regularly exposed to soft skills sessions, activities and those who are deprived of the same.

Keywords: Soft skills, Soft skills training programme

INTRODUCTION

The education scenario in the recent times is changing very fast. No matter how well equipped an individual think he is with respect to the technical skills he will not get success in the corporate world. Communication skill is an important soft skills element and plays an important task in the business world.

Soft skills have become a crucial and increasingly sort after quality for careers in corporate world, irrespective of the sector. Requirement of soft skills in a job has made the competition for job acquisition and job sustainability tougher. All those candidates who wish to get an edge over their competitor are expected to improve their soft skills so that they will be able to come out as

a winner irrespective of the hurdles that they face in the employment procedure. The global competitiveness of Indian industry and also its employment generation potential is clearly dependent on availability of required skills and trained personnel. Soft skills are different and distinct from Hard Skills .Soft skills are those skills that add more significance to the hard skills ornamented by an individual.

Soft skills are perceived as those capabilities that inherent in an individual. These competencies exist in every individual a particular level. But if these skills are not used or if the individual who adorns these skills. Individual is unaware of it then that individual will never be able to utilize his / her inherent skills.

DEFINITION

Soft skills are essentially people's skills or personality specific skills. According to Hewitt Sean (2008) soft skills are "non-technical, intangible, personality specific skills" which determines an individual's strength as "a leader, listener and negotiator, or as a conflict mediator". Soft skills are the traits and abilities of attitude and behaviour rather than of knowledge or technical aptitude.

OBJECTIVE OF SOFT SKILLS TRAINING PROGRAMMES

The main objectives of the soft skills training imparted to MBA students should be to:

1. To develop communication skills (spoken and written).
2. To identify the skills required to perform up to the standards in interview.
3. Make the student capable with respect to the current Job requirements, by expanding the skills set.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Method: Data collected for the research topic is from secondary sources.

CORE ELEMENTS IN SOFT SKILL

1. FORMAL HANDSHAKE

First impression is formed while an interaction between two individuals happen and handshake is the first point of contact. There are important fundamentals to remember when having a formal handshake.

ESSENTIAL POINTS FOR GOOD FORMAL HANDSHAKE

1. Maintain a good eye to eye contact with the other person.
2. Smile when a formal handshake is done.
3. Have a firm grip but don't crush the other person's hand.

4. Be confident and introduce yourself to the other person.
5. Leave the hand after few seconds of handshake.
6. In a handshake with lady. The lady has offer for a handshake first.

2. GROUP DISCUSSION

Presenting the different ideas on a particular topic in a systematic way and also listening to the others when points are made differentiates the individuals who attend a group discussion and aim for employment and the end of the day. A standard group discussion happens for 10 to 12 minutes with 8 to 10 members participating.

There is key area in a group discussion which the company look for and judge while selecting the candidates. The number of individuals selected for future process based on the vacancy in the organization.

POINTS TO REMEMBER FOR GROUP DISCUSSION

1. Keep eye to eye contact while speaking.
2. Initiate the Group Discussion and also allow others to speak
3. Speak clearly and use facts and figures relating to topic to justify
4. Make sure to bring the discussion on track
5. Positive attitude
6. Listen carefully to others (important quality to become a good manager)
7. Formal dressing

QUALITY'S JUDGED IN GROUP DISCUSSION

1. How good is the communication with others
2. Behaviour and interaction with group.
3. How open minded is the individual.
4. Listening skill.
5. How are the views and idea put forward to the group

3. FACE TO FACE INTERVIEW

Making the students aware and prepare them for a few expected questions which will be asked in the interview is the smart work placement officer has to do in order to have more numbers of students placed out of the students appearing for interview.

TIPS REGARDING INTERVIEW AND THE ATTIRE

1. Research the potential employer
2. Review the job description and match your experience and education with the duties of the position
3. Prepare a 1 to 2 minute script about yourself.
4. Be sure to arrive 10 to 15 minutes prior to the start of the interview
5. Greet the interviewer with a firm handshake
6. Maintain good eye contact and posture

7. Make sure you are energetic and enthusiastic
8. Speak clearly and articulate

STANDARD INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

1. Would you tell me about yourself?
2. What is your greatest strength?
3. What is your greatest weakness?
4. Where do you see yourself in 5 years?
5. What about this position do you find most appealing?
6. Why do you want to work for our company?
7. Why should we hire you?

CONCLUSION

Today, new generation managers are expected to garnish soft skills along with the technical/hard skills. The modern corporate managers should have the talent to understand situations, fill in the missing conversations, capacity to connect and coordinate, and should know how to enlist the support from others. The ability to work in team and good interpersonal skills definitely add worth in the growth and promotion of corporate executive. The research results show that soft skills of the students can be refined if management colleges pass on the adequately framed and standardized soft skills training sessions to them. Students who are regularly exposed to soft skills sessions will have an edge over other students not only with respect to employability but also with respect to overall personality growth.

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Paper 7
**ROLE OF ON-LINE TUTORING IN THE INDIAN
SCENARIO**

Panchajanyeswari M Achar

Faculty, College of Information Science and Computer Science
City Campus, Pandeshwar,
Srinivas University
Mangalore – 575 001

E-mail: jahnavi.murali@rediffmail.com

Abstract:

India is a country where education practices are at their best. Indian parents want to impart quality education to their children irrespective of where they live. Most of the Indians who migrate to foreign countries for lucrative jobs want to give the best education to their wards. This is where online tutoring comes to existence. Over the last few years, online tutoring from India for students across the globe has taken on the contours of an industry. Online tutoring is a big segment in parallel education, which is expected to grow in a rapid pace. Indian e-tutoring companies reach out to the students across the globe. Online tutoring is the best job that can lure Indian women who would like to become a good homemaker without sacrificing her career. Online tutoring is conducted by companies who hire tutors, who are available on demand. Thus, online tutoring from India plays a vital role which is driven by availability of large pool of talented teachers at lower costs. This paper highlights the working mode of on-line tutoring in the context of Indian women who find it difficult to juggle between home and office. The paper also focuses on the impact of online tutoring in the Indian market. This paper also does a comparative study of a few online tutoring companies to analyze their growth. This paper highlights the future of e-learning in the Indian context.

Keywords: online tutoring, e-learning, e-tutoring companies, on-line learning

Introduction:

Students from primary classes to Class XII are now actively leveraging websites and apps in their search for excellent tutors. In the last few years, the approach of the parent, teacher, and student fraternity in India has been veering towards the online world, especially in urban and semi-urban India. A handful of startups rode high on this behavioral change and succeeded in the online tutoring domain. Online tutoring is not just about connecting teachers and students. It should have the ability to map coaching to respective curriculum and syllabus. To succeed, the companies need to have a good tutor management platform, robust training, remote monitoring of tutors, and tools and techniques using analytics and artificial intelligence(AI) to ensure an

effective outcome for each student[1]. But preserving the retention rate of students and minimizing the attrition rate of tutors will define the growth and sustainability of a company in this domain.

A teacher is a trained professional who teaches a group of students. Teachers' pay rates vary considerably depending on the grade level that is being taught, the level of education that the teacher has, which state they reside in and whether the position is full-time or part-time[2]. When you work as an employee, you don't have to invest any money up front or find your own clients, but your pay rate, work hours, and how you work will be more restricted. A tutor, on the other hand, is an informal professional who gives individuals additional or remedial instruction in a given subject[3]. While you need to have extensive knowledge of a subject, you don't need any specialized training to be a tutor. When a woman works as a tutor, she can be hired on as an employee, independent contractor, or can choose to open up your own home-based tutoring business. When you set up your own business, you have more flexibility with scheduling, choosing clients, and setting your rates, but you'll also have to find your own customers, set up your business, and pay self-employment taxes. Establishing a tutoring business is easy and has relatively low start-up costs. Some items you'll need to get started are a phone line or Smartphone, a computer, high-speed internet access, a printer and scanner, and a website to market your business.

The demand for online tutoring from India is driven by its large talent pool of teachers and lower costs. This is similar to the demand for the well-established Indian software and services and business process outsourcing industries. Then there is the advantage of sheer convenience. In most of these companies, online tutors are available 24 hours a day for one-on-one help. Students can log in at their convenience and assignments can be discussed through online chat sessions and voice. A virtual whiteboard allows the use of charts, graphs and diagrams.

Impact of online tutoring on Indian economy:

Over the last few years, online tutoring from India for students across the globe has taken on the contours of an industry. Along with other services in the burgeoning person-to-person off-shoring (PPO) space, it has tremendous growth potential: In the U.S. market alone, revenues for Indian tutoring companies are estimated by some to be at \$20 million today, and industry players expect the total to reach \$2 billion in three to five years [5].

While there are no firm numbers about the industry's size, estimates suggest that well over 100 players fill the space. They range in size from the venture-fund backed TutorVista.com, which has 600 tutors and 10,000 students, to Tutors Worldwide India, a fully-owned subsidiary of the U.S. Company Socratic Learning, with 250 tutors [6]. There are also mom-and-pop outfits with five tutors or fewer. Science, mathematics and English are usually taught. Offerings include homework help, regular grade tutoring, and preparation for the SAT, ACT and other exams. In many cases, tutors work from their homes. Though prices vary, they are much lower than those at U.S. tutoring firms, in some cases as low as \$10 an hour. TutorVista.com, which charges \$99.99 per month for unlimited tutoring, aims to make its service part of a family's monthly budget, like a health club membership.

A recent research puts online tutoring from India as one of the PPO services to watch out for. Others with strong growth potential are website development, graphic design, and editorial and writing services [7]. According to the research, the growth of the Internet, small offices, home businesses and individuals depends on the technological advancements and they can as well utilize PPO services. Individually taken, each contract is often of low value, usually between \$100 and \$5,000. Since the number of end consumers and small businesses is enormous, the total addressable market in the United States alone easily exceeds \$20 billion. Indian e-tutoring companies haven't forayed only into the United States [8]. They are also reaching out to students in the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, China and West Asia. But it is the U.S. online tutoring market, currently estimated at \$200 million and which some players say represents more than half the global market. TutorVista, for instance, has students in 13 countries, but more than 90% of its revenues come from the United States.

Business models in online tutoring:

Indian companies who are already in the education business and start-ups have been quick to spot these opportunities and are trying out different business models. Some companies, like Educomp Solutions and TransTutors, have tied up with U.S. e-tutoring firms and get work subcontracted from them[9]. As the back-end vendors for the U.S. firms, these Indian companies put up the infrastructure and hire and train tutors in India. In most cases, the course content is provided by the U.S. Company, which also performs the marketing, brand building and student acquisition.

Another business model that companies, including TutorVista, have adopted is the direct-to-consumer route [10]. Along with the back-end operations, these companies develop course content and reach out to students directly. Some companies, such as Career Launcher, started their e-tutoring operations as back-end providers, learned the ropes, and then branched out to the retail segment [11]. Others are keeping both options open, a strategy they obviously prefer to keep under wraps for fear of upsetting their U.S. partners.

Each of these business models has its own opportunities and challenges. While the subcontracting model has a low gestation period, it is also very competitive. With an eye toward getting the work, Indian companies tend to undercut each other. The result is low margins, around 10% [12]. On the other hand, the direct-to-consumer model offers much higher margins, around 25% to 30% [13]. But it requires large up-front investments for brand building and customer acquisition.

Conclusion:

In this paper, the primary differences between tutor and teacher along with their pros and cons have been highlighted. The paper also reflects the economic growth of online tutoring in the Indian business scenario. The paper throws light on the different business models in online tutoring along with their opportunities and challenges. Some examples of online business companies and their growth in the Indian market have been discussed. To sum up, online tutoring helps individuals, especially women to devote their time to work as well as to their domestic affairs. Online tutoring helps to boost the country's economy by outsourcing our talent

to all over the world. The future of online tutoring seems to be very promising for both the tutors as well as the learners’.

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Paper 8
**SMART BIN: SMART MONITORING SYSTEM TO
KEEP OUR CITY CLEAN**

Sangeetha Prabhu¹, & Krishna Prasad K.²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science,
Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University,
Mangalore, India

E-mail: sangeethaprabhu96@gmail.com

Abstract:

The Internet of Things is a rapidly changing concept. The Internet is now a manner of existence with the World becoming linked via the Internet. For all our fundamental requirements, we also need the Internet, say for bank account management, grocery shopping, travel arrangements management, the list is infinite. Most of the appliances (“things”) we use it on a regular basis are regulated on in our own mobile devices only by remotes and sometimes by apps. This has resulted into its own “network” and is also frequently referred to as the “Internet of Things”. Using the IoT, all the facilities we use in our daily lives can be monitored and controlled. Most of the process is achieved in IoT using sensors. Everywhere, detectors are created and these devices transform pure physical information into digital signals and deliver them to their command core. Through the Internet, we can track environmental changes remotely from a corner of the world. I work the same way with the mixture of detectors namely IR detector smart selection bin. The IR detector will demonstrate us the different trash concentrations in the dustbins and push their performance forward when they cross their limit level. The NodeMCU also receives this information and the NodeMCU provides the transmitter unit the information. A mobile phone is linked to the client in the receiver segment to display information of the garbage bin on the HTML site in our mobile phone's web browser. In this document we will evaluate internet stuff, IoT background, intelligent dustbins and their work, apps and disadvantages of intelligent dustbin

Keywords: IoT, Smart bin, Technology, Sensors, Internet.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's way of living, the Internet and its applications are an integral part of human life. In all respects, it has become an extremely useful tool. Because of the enormous demand and necessity, scientists have not just connected computers to a web. These studies led to the development of an interesting Internet of Things. Internet communications have grown from user to user: interaction to devices: interactions with devices. The ideas of IoT were introduced years ago, but are still in the earlier stage of practical application. Through IoT, the domestic robotics and transport sectors are expanding rapidly. Seeing that most operations are performed via the

internet they need an efficient fast internet connection the software can be easily explained as a link between computers. The IoT will regulate and track all the hardware we use in our lives today. Many operations are conducted using IoT sensors. Sensors are distributed all over the site, and raw physical information is delivered to the control centre. This allows us to track modifications of the atmosphere directly via the Internet from any corner of the world. Smart collection bin appears similar in integrating sensors such as weight sensors and IR sensors that indicate their corresponding weights and stages. The IR sensors inform us all the various waste levels in the dustbins and also trigger the weight detector so that when the maximum limit is reached the data can be sent ahead. The microcontroller (ARMLPC2148) is provided further data and the controller provides the transmitting module (Wi-Fi module) with the knowledge. A mobile device must be linked to the WLAN router at the recipient section to demonstrate all the details of the waste bin on the HTML tab in our portable handset's browser[1].

2. OBJECTIVES

Smart waste disposal is a proposal where we can deal with a large number of environmental damage and disease issues that disturb society. Waste management must be carried out instantly otherwise irregular management will have a negative impact on nature. The regulation of intelligent waste is primarily consistent with the Smart Cities idea. Our suggested system's key objectives are as follows:

1. Waste disposal monitoring.
2. Provision for smart disposal device engineering.
3. Avoiding contact of human beings.
4. Human effort and energy management.
5. Lead in a nurturing environment that is waste-free.

This project is part of the integrated systems as well as android application development category.

3. TYPES AND METHODS OF WASTE DISPOSAL

The waste created by various sections of the community can be categorized by its form (physical characteristics) and target. Such distinction is important because it allows systematic selection, reuse and the concept of the best goal simpler. The waste disposed of in urban communities constitutes a highly large and diverse volume of material and a much more homogeneous bunch of manufacturing and hospital waste [2]. A selective collection is usually the foundation of proper waste disposal and the world's main method of recycling. For an IoT-based waste management system, classification should be done early and specific containers should be taken into consideration for each type of waste. For example, solid waste disposal is undertaken in London in compliance with specific collection criteria. It uses disposal or various colored bins like red toxic waste; yellow clinic waste; blue disinfection hospital waste; white food waste; green bottles of glass, dark and brown, in different boxes and types [3]. The following are then characterized the various types of waste labeled:

- **Organic Waste:** It is also the waste only from organic waste [4]. They are also mainly produced in private residences, restaurants and shopping centers that work only with

food. They need to be physically separated from other waste because most of them are for municipal waste.

- **Recyclable Waste:** All garbage cans also are used for transformation into other components or for the production of raw materials [5]. It is created in households, enterprises, and industries and needs to be segregated in order for specific collection groups to collect and distribute in cooperatives and recycling companies for the end of storage.
- **Industrial Waste:** These are the primarily firm residues that occur in the manufacturing production process. It usually contains remains of raw resources destined for manufacturing recyclables or reuse [6].
- **Hospital Waste:** This is the waste that comes from hospitals and doctors clinics and can contaminate the individual and transmit illnesses to contacts [7]. It must be treated with feasible care in accordance with established procedures. This kind of waste is intended for the medical care of companies where it will be normally incinerated.
- **Commercial Waste:** This is the production of clothing, toys and equipment produced by commercial enterprises. Almost all of these wastes are for recycling [8].
- **Green Waste:** This is the fabric that comes primarily from the cutting of trees, sections, trunks, barks, and street leaves. It is used for organic waste and generating organic fertilizers as it is organic matter [9].
- **Electronic Waste:** It's a waste generated from the disposal of materials that are not functioning or outdated by consumer electronics [10]. They ship this waste to a atmosphere in a manner that is not damaging.
- **Nuclear Waste:** It is primarily provided by nuclear power stations. It is very dangerous since it is a radioactive element and must be processed in compliance with strict security standards [11].

4. ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: Signal Transmitter

Fig 2: Signal Receiver

5. WORKING

The Ultrasonic Sensor, PIC, GSM as well as GPS bin will convey the database with the coordinate and bin status. In this scenario GSM is the network client that holds the limited rate Internet SIM. A bin status is regulated by the ultrasonic sensor that uses ultrasonic waves. Use the PIC controller board for ultrasound, GSM and GPS sensor control. The database maintains the uncompleted bins, loaded bins and identification of the jurisdiction. Whenever the daily or licensed client gathers and demands the details from the server. The data for the user is just about the nearest empty bin as well as the coordinated containers will be provided to the authorized person. The client end includes the Android-compatible phone-based app. Two distinct user and authority pins will be provided. The user tells the closest unfulfilled bin of the route, and the designated individual notifies the completed containers of the direction. The job is just as follows, the client puts the garbage in to the container, the tests on threshold level, the state and the directions to the test center after entering the right level, the testing center utilizes multifunctional Bins 'coordinates which gives an optimal direction to the garbage truck.

6. COMPONENTS USED

- **Ultrasonic Sensor:**

To calculate the distance, ultrasonic detectors shown in the figure are used. It consists essentially of a four pin board, VCC, Trigger, Echo and Ground. It consists of an ultrasonic transmitter, receiver and unit of control. The popularly used ultrasonic sensors with Arduino ARM, Raspberry Pie etc. The sensor head transmits a wave of ultrasound and receives from the destination a wave reflected. The distance can be determined by the time measure between the emission and the receipt. That is $L=1/2*t*c$, where L is the distance, t is the time between both the transmitted emission and the receipt and c is the sonic speed.

Fig 3: Ultrasonic Sensor

- **ESP 8266 – 01**

The Esp8266-01 System is indeed a reduced power microcontroller specializing in the design of reduced-power communication devices, including Bluetooth & Wi-Fi connection packages. It needs an input of 3.3 vs. and draws low power that can be used for a long period of time. There are 2 available GPIO pins used to build separate pairs of transmitters, switches and detectors. The built-in ESP 8266 Wi-Fi chip allows you to link to the LAN.

Fig 4: ESP 8266 – 01

- **Node MCU**

NodeMCU seems to be an IoT platform free software. NodeMCU implies a firmware instead of a deployment tool, as shown in this figure NodeMCU traffic around firebase sensors is monitored It consists from both the HCSR04 and MQ136, which communicate digital and analog I / O pins. This is a 12E variant of the Esp-8266 microcontroller module. The Electronic Analog Converter (DAC) has a huge number of GPIO pins and it can interpret analog sensor value. Unlike with the ESP board model 01, NodeMCU supports multiple sensors and integrations at a faster processing speed.

Fig 5: Node MCU

7. ADVANTAGES

- The application of intelligent waste disposal to an area optimizes management, material and cost, making it an intelligent city.
- This allows executives to generate additional income from smart device advertising

- This saves a lot of time through using adaptive trash collection containers and fill-level sensors. Trucks only make the journey to the loaded containers and bins as intelligent transport. This eliminates up to 30% the costs of construction, maintenance.
- Reduces traffic congestion and noise due to decreased environmental pollution as a consequence of less vehicles for collecting on highways.
- The two-way interaction between smart bins and system operators has been effective.
- Keeps your clean, green and odourless atmosphere, stresses the healthier environment and makes the cities more enchanting.
- It minimizes the work requirements in the process of waste collection.
- The system needs more containers per population of the city for independent garbage collection. This result in increased initial cost compared to many other techniques due to costly, intelligent dustbins.
- The persons involved in smart waste disposal systems must receive training.

8. DISADVANTAGES

- The system needs more containers per total population for different storage of waste. This leads to a high base cost compared with other techniques due to costly smart bins.
- This reduces labour demands which lead to increased job losses for unqualified people.
- The individuals involved in the smart waste disposal process have to be educated.

9. CONCLUSION

Adoption of the IR detector, Microcontroller as well as Wi-Fi module smart trash monitoring system. This system ensures that the dustbins are cleaned as long as the waste reaches its peak. If the bins are not emptied in a certain period, the report shall be sent to competent authorities who will be allowed to take the appropriate action against company concerned. It also allows to track fraudulent reports and can thus reduce corruption throughout the system. This reduces the overall set of trash collection vehicles trips and thus reduces waste collection costs. It keeps society clean, at the end of the day.

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Paper 9
**MEASURES TO PREVENT CRIME AGAINST WOMEN
IN INDIA**

Pradeep M. D.¹ & Ranjan A. V.²

¹Assistant Professor, Social Work Department, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India.

Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

²Medial Social Worker, Indian Cancer Society Mangalore, Karnataka

Email: ranjankanathila14@gmail.com

Abstract:

Rigveda depicts women with highest respect in the Indian society. Volumes can be written on the heroic deeds of Indian women since from Vedic to modern times. But the social, political and economic changes lead towards the deterioration of women status. Many evil customs and traditions stepped in which enslaved the women and tied them to the boundaries of the house. The official statistics recorded declining sex-ratio, health status, literacy rate, work participation rate and political participation. Other hand, social evils including dowry deaths, child marriages, domestic violence, rape, sexual harassment and exploitation started to spread in the society. New evils including humiliation, rape, kidnapping, molestation, honor killing, torture abuse started to spread. The society which cannot respect, protect and nurture its women and children loses moral moorings running adrift. The plight of women is not likely to change as the time started to watch helplessly the suffering of women in the form of discrimination, oppression, exploitation, degradation, aggression and humiliation. India patriarchal system has suppressed and subjugated the women's life to a greater extent. Indian society believed clinging on to the orthodox beliefs causing brunt of violence in the form of public, physical, emotional and moral damages. Violence against women has become the world wide phenomena. This paper review about various forms of crimes committed against women, the strategies to curb these evils, future prospective to empower women to contribute to the national growth.

Keywords: Women, Crime, Violence, Exploitation, Humiliation, Orthodox, Empowerment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian society considers women as the second class citizens even though we represent goddesses like Durga, Saraswati, Parvati and Kali to women. Women face the problems in acceptance due to the male dominant society which resulted in the deterioration of their status. Even though women devotes their life towards family are not able to get share in the parental property, medical care and education depriving their equality. Indian Constitution guarantees women with equality, dignity and protection from exploitation. Poverty demands women's participation in economic activities. History of India replicates women status as high in the ancient times, low in the medieval period, equal during reformatory ages varying with time. Violence against women gets social sanction from the gender superiority prevailing in the society men superior over women. The semantic meaning of crime is causing direct or indirect physical or mental cruelty to women such as Child marriages, infanticide, Sati, Sexual harassment, Dowry, physical aggressions, physical abuse, hanging, trafficking, intimidation, stalking, abuse, female genital mutilation, eve-teasing, rape, mental pressure, battering, maltreatment, cohesion, blackmails, emotional threats, control over speech and actions, domestic violence, eve-teasing, molestation, bigamy, fraudulent marriage, adultery,

cruelty, abduction of married women, kidnapping, harassment at working place, no minimum legal protection and abuse of elderly female. Crime against single working women is due to the lack of infrastructure to those who leave their families for working away from home. Any act or omission harmful to the society and punishable by law amounts to crime [1]. Social violence including forcing the daughter in law for foeticide harms the society [2]. In 1993, The United Nations defined ‘Violence against Women’ in the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women as an act of gender-based violence resulting in the physical, sexual or psychological harm to women whether occurring in public or private life. [3]

2. TYPES OF CRIMES

Among the enormous amount of crimes against women most prominent are explained below.

- Domestic Violence: Any violence including harassment, maltreatment, brutality, assault, intimidation by way of hitting, kicking, biting, shoving, restraining, throwing etc committed at home by the family members.
- Son Preferences: It results in female infanticide through neglect of girl child without providing nutrition, health care and education.
- Dowry and Early Marriage: Payment of bride money resulting in the dowry deaths and early marriages deprive the girls from the right of education.
- Trafficking: The economic and social conditions of women force them to be pushing to the rackets of trafficking.
- Rape: One quarter of the reported rapes involves girls under the age of 16.
- Sexual Assault within the Marriage: As wife is expected to submit causing many sexual assaults which are difficult to prove without serious injuries.
- Sexual Harassment: Harassment through eve teasing, sexual abuse at workplace is increasing due to the influence of western culture.
- Violence against unorganised Labourers: The discrimination in the payment of wage.
- Female Genital Mutilation: World Health Organization reports about some forms of female genital mutilation and its adverse health hazards by 85 million to 115 million girls and women.
- Pornography: It replicates women as mere receptacles for lust.
- Custodial Violence: Members of custodians violates and commits crimes including rape, assault etc.
- Armed Conflicts: Many innocent women were raped during the armed conflicts.
- Incest: Incest is sexual activity between family members and close relatives. This may include sexual activity between people in a consanguineous relationship (blood relations), or related by affinity, such as members of the same household, step relatives, those related by adoption or marriage, or members of the same clan or lineage.[4]
- Commodification of Women: Women are used as commodities in trafficking with little control over their body and life.
- Female Infanticides and Sex selective Abortions: High masculine sex ratio in India can be attributed to female infanticides and sex-selective abortions.
- Trafficking: Women are forced into prostitution, child labour and exploitation.

- Dowry: A traditional social practice, dowry is the ritual of a bride's family giving cash and/or goods to the family of the groom, as an accompaniment to their giving away the bride. IT emerged to be a cultural phenomena for the people of all castes and class [5]
- Child Marriage: Due to poverty many children below the age of 18 years were married leading to health problems and malnutrition.
- Eve-Teasing: Eve teasing is an act of terror that violates a woman's body, space and self-respect by making women to feel inferior, weak and afraid.
- Acid Attacks: Acid is used to disfigure or kill women against the issues of family feuds, inability to meet dowry demands and for rejection of marriage proposals.

3. CONSTITUTIONAL & LEGAL PROVISIONS ON WOMEN

The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Duties and Directive Principles. It not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the State to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women for neutralizing the cumulative socio economic, education and political disadvantages faced by them. Within the framework of a democratic polity, our laws, development policies, Plans and programmes have aimed at women's advancement in different spheres. India has also ratified Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women in 1993. [6]. Article 14, confers on men and women equal rights and opportunities in political, economic and social sphere. Article 15, prohibits, discrimination against any citizen on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex etc. Article 16, provides for equality of opportunities matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the state. Article 39(a)(d), mentions policy security of state equality for both men and women the right to a means of livelihood and equal pay for equal work for both men and women. Article 42, Direct the State to make provision for ensuring just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief. Legal provisions such as *Factories Act 1948*: Under this Act, a woman cannot be forced to work beyond 8 hours and prohibits employment of women except between 6 A.M. and 7 P.M. *Maternity Benefit Act 1961*: A Woman is entitled 12 weeks maternity leave with full wages. *The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961*: Under the provisions of this Act demand of dowry either before marriage, during marriage and or after the marriage is an offence. *The Equal Remuneration Act of 1976*: This act provides equal wages for equal work: It provides for the payment of equal wages to both men and women workers for the same work or work of similar nature. It also prohibits discrimination against women in the matter of recruitment. *The Child Marriage Restrain Act of 1976*: This act raises the age for marriage of a girl to 18 years from 15 years and that of a boy to 21 years. *Indian Penal Code*: Section 354 and 509 safeguards the interests of women. *The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act of 1971*: The Act safeguards women from unnecessary and compulsory abortions. Amendments to Criminal Law 1983, which provides for a punishment of 7 years in ordinary cases and 10 years for custodial rape cases. *73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment Act* reserved 1/3rd seats in Panchayat and Urban Local Bodies for women. *The National Commission for Women Act, 1990*. The act such as *The Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993*, *Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005*, *Protection of Women against Sexual Harassment at Workplace Bill, 2010*: on November 4, 2010, the Government introduced protection of Women Against Sexual Harassment at Workplace Bill, 2010, which aims at protecting the women at

workplace not only to women employee but also to female clients, customer, students, research scholars in colleges and universities patients in hospitals. The Bill was passed in Lok Sabha on 3.9.2012. Although women may be victims of any of the general crimes such as ‘murder’, ‘robbery’, ‘cheating’, etc. only the crimes which are directed specifically against women are characterised as ‘crimes against women’. Various new legislations have been brought and amendments have been made in existing laws with a view to handle these crimes effectively. These are broadly classified under two categories.

(1) The Crimes under the Indian Penal Code (IPC): Rape (Sec. 376 IPC), Attempt to commit rape (Sec 376/511 IPC), Kidnapping & abduction of women (Section 363,364,364A, 366 IPC), Dowry deaths (Section 304B IPC), Assault on woman with intent to outrage her modesty (Sec. 354 IPC), Sexual harassment (Sec.354A IPC), Assault on woman with intent to outrage her modesty (Sec. 354C IPC), Voyeurism (Sec. 354D IPC), Others, Insult to the modesty of women (Sec. 509 IPC), Cruelty by husband or his relatives, (Sec. 498A IPC), Importation of girl from foreign country (up to 21 years of age) (Sec. 366 B IPC), Abetment of suicide of women (Sec. 306 IPC).

(2) The Crimes under the Special & Local Law: Although all laws are not gender specific, the provisions of law affecting women significantly have been reviewed periodically and amendments carried out to keep pace with the emerging requirements. The gender specific laws for which crime statistics are recorded throughout the country are The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, The Indecent Representation of Women Prohibition Act, 1986, The Commission of Sati Prevention Act, 1987 , The Protection of women from domestic Violence Act, 2005, The Immoral Traffic Prevention Act, 1956. Empowerment of women guarantees dignified life at the threshold of providing them with social justice. The most effective strategies are likely to be those that support women to organize peer groups and mobilize community resources and public services, including women’s health services. Such approaches enable women to overcome resignation to the legitimacy of the established order are important factor in the perpetuation of imbalances of power between women and men. If women are to implement their reproductive preferences, then it is essential that their empowerment occur not only within their personal spheres, but also in the broader spheres of the community and the state. Although special provisions, affirmative action and reservations in education, employment and political life may have their own advantages, more fundamental than these are creation of a dependable legal framework for protection of their bodily integrity and personal autonomy. A multi-pronged approach for an all-round development of women by setting into service different provisions of the constitution might be more appropriate. The post emergency due process revolution, public interest litigation and judicial activism animating positive dimensions of right to life have made the right to life and due process jurisprudence interestingly more rewarding for women. The declining sex ratio in India amply portrays the discrimination shown towards women at the stage of birth. The crimes against women in India are growing at a rampant speed. Women, irrespective of their class, caste and educational status, are not safe. The lack of any serious effort to rectify the weaknesses in dealing with the crimes against women further. [7] The official statistics showed a declining sex-ratio, health status, literacy rate, work participation rate and political participation among women.

4. CONCLUSION

It is inevitable to create an environment where, women can make independent decisions. Education is the weapon to overcome these inequalities. The semantic meaning of 'crime against women' is direct or indirect physical or mental cruelty to women. Various kinds of violence against women are eve-teasing, molestation, bigamy, fraudulent marriage, adultery and enticement of married women abduction and kidnapping, rape, harassment to women at work ing place, wife beating, dowry death, female child abuse and abuse of elderly female etc. Rape is a crime not only against the person of a woman it is a crime against the entire society. It destroys the entire psychology of a woman and pushes her into deep emotional crisis. Rape is therefore the most hated crime. Crime against women includes any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or private life. Although women may be victims of any of the general crimes such as 'murder', 'robbery', 'cheating', etc, only the crimes which are directed specifically against women are characterized as 'crimes against women'. Various new legislations have been brought and amendments have been made in existing laws with a view to handle these crimes effectively. Only legislation and law enforcement agencies cannot prevent the incident of crime against women. There is need of social awakening and change in the attitude of masses, so that due respect and equal status is given to women. It is a time when the women need to be given her due. This awakening can be brought by education campaign among youth making them aware of existing social evils and the means to eradicate same. Women and feminist organisations are serious in pursuing the constitutional and legal means of attaining justice, both individual and social. All India Democratic Women's Association, Manila Dakshita Samiti and Delhi Domestic Women's Forum have been remarkably successful in lawyering for justice to women suggests the need for consolidating the gains of concerted efforts of women in future. It determined to take constitutional litigation as a sword of remedies with continuous, systematic and well coordinated efforts. Extension of legal literacy and legal clinical service for women with the assistance of lawyers and law teachers goes a long way in this direction. Free and Compulsory education, Freedom to hold high offices, Political rights to franchise and contest in elections, Spouses sharing a common social life in cities are the recent trends.[8] . Almost every woman has experienced the feeling of being mistreated, trivialized, kept out, put down, ignored, assaulted, laughed at or discriminated against because of her gender.[9]. Many evil customs and traditions stepped in which enslaved the women and tied them to the boundaries of the house. [10]. Humiliation, rape, kidnapping, molestation, dowry death, torture, wife-beating etc.have grown up over the years. [11]

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Paper 10

ONLINE EDUCATION: A WAY FOR REALIZING THE DREAMS TO LEARN

Dr. Gaonkar Gopalakrishna M.¹ & Manjunath M.²

¹Associate Professor and Head, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College and Centre for PG Studies, Tenkanidiyoor, Udupi, Karantaka, India.

Email: gmgakonkar40@gmail.com

² Lecturer in Economics, Richard Almeida Memorial College, Navunda, Kundapur Taluk, Karnataka, India.

Email: golihole143@gmail.com

Abstract:

Online education is becoming a popular mode of imparting education to those who are in very need and thrust of learning new and advanced knowledge. Online teaching is gradually replacing the conventional class room methods of education because, E-learning or e-education programs can offer wider content on a topic than the conventional education lesson: in a conventional class the learners are limited to the amount of information that they can get but online education is a dynamic industry, with new technologies and instructional strategies always on the horizon. No doubt, Behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism are the three broad learning theories most often utilized in the creation of instructional environments. But, these theories were developed in a time when learning was not impacted through technology. With the progress in technology and the advancement in learning connectivism provides insight into learning skills. The paper tries to examine, the forms, plus points and shortcomings of online education. The main forms are Web-based learning, virtual classroom learning, learning **through** Mobile, Video-based Learning etc. Major plus points, convenient, cost effective, job oriented, etc, and a few short comings, lack of awareness, inadequate technology, language barriers, etc. are discussed in brief.

Keywords: Online Education, Internet, Learning, Skill and Connectivism.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, online education is becoming a popular mode of imparting education to those who are in very need and thrust of learning new and advanced knowledge. Online teaching is gradually replacing the conventional class room methods of education because, E-learning or e-education programs can offer wider content on a topic than the conventional education lesson. In a conventional class the learners are limited to the certain amount of information that they can get but online education is a dynamic industry, with new technologies and instructional strategies. But, the field of education has been slow to recognize both the impact

of new learning tools and the environmental changes in what it means to learn. The New Media Consortium's 2016 Horizon Report expects "increasing use of blended learning designs" to strongly impact online learning over the next two years (New Media Consortium, 2016). The Connectivism provides insight into learning skills and tasks needed for learners to flourish in a digital era. (George Siemens) In the light of the above views, the paper tries to examine, the forms and plus and minus of online education.

2. OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY

To study the forms of the online Education, To know the plus points of online education and to examine the shortcomings of online education. This study is purely a descriptive study, it is carried out with the help of available secondary data, published reports and research articles in journals and edited books.

3. MEANING OF ONLINE EDUCATION

E learning is an approach to teaching and learning, representing all or part of the educational model applied, that is based on the use of electronic media and devices as tools for improving access. The introduction of computers was the basis of this revolution and with the passage of time, as we get hooked to smartphones, tablets, etc, these devices now have an importance place in the classrooms for learning. Thus, E-learning involves the use of a computer or electronic device (e.g. a mobile phone) to provide training, educational or learning material (Derek Stockley 2003)

4. FORMS OF ONLINE EDUCATION:

As per the study, online education can be imparted in different ways. Here, it is tried to summarize a few among them. Computer-Based Training, CD-ROM Based Learning, Web-Based Learning, Virtual Classroom Learning, Learning through Mobile, Collective Learning, Video based learning, custom e learning, Off the shelf e learning, learning through webinars. Thus, above mentioned are a few e-Learning forms. Today a number of platforms are coming up to deliver E-education throughout the world. Example, MOOC, COURSERA, Etc.

5. PLUS POINTS OF ONLINE EDUCATION

Online education is realizing the dreams of learning or acquiring the knowledge of many people in the world. It carries a number of merits particularly in technically advanced country. Flexible Scheduling, means you can schedule your time according your free time or available time, so it is more convenient. Online learning saves money because no travelling cost, accommodation cost and more fees. It is easily affordable. Every individual learn according his face of learning, he is not suppose to depend on friends or peers in the process of his learning. This way of learning is best suits to job holders, they can fulfill their dream of learning and satisfy their hunger of knowledge, means pursue a Job along with Studies. Any one who have internet connection can easily access to learning materials, this is the biggest plus point learners. When there is no need to travel, no need to attend not important classes, learner can save lot of time. It can meet a specific learning objective, because the majority online courses are aim and outcome oriented. if the learner study a course with a specific objective, definitely he fulfills it.

Geographical distance, in online education, will not be the barrier to the learner, a person from any corner of the world, can access and earn knowledge without any problem. There are a number of self paced courses, there is no time bound to take the course thus, pursue study whenever, wherever. These courses reduce the cost of education to the possible level. No transport cost, no material cost, only examination fee, means, cost of getting education is bare minimum. Totally, it is in right sense possibilities of dream come true to a innumerable of education aspirants across the world.

6. SHORTCOMINGS OF ONLINE LEARNING

Online education is not free from minus points or shortcomings. Of course, to take any positive steps in the world, there is always some challenges. Here we bring forth some challenges in the field of online education. Majority in the world are not aware about these type of education, probably it may take several years to reach who are in need of it. There is insufficient digital infrastructure in many countries of the world. It is so because there is no proper internet connection, computers, power supply and other needy materials. In a class room condition teacher observes, motivates student on the base of students interest and attitude. In an online learning a lazy learner some time drop the course or not studies up to the mark because lack of motivation. Regarding the credibility of degree there is still ambiguity among people because a number of fraudulent courses are in operation, they do not have any credentials in their certificates. The biggest drawback of online learning is limited social interaction. Since online education can be accessed at home or any other convenient place, there is very limited direct interaction with the teacher and other people doing the course. Language of the course is another major barrier, for example :India is a multi-linguistic country, and a vast majority of the population comes from rural areas. They may not understand English, which is considered as world language. In such condition interested learners hesitate to take the course. Overdependence on technology can be a major drawback in online learning mode of education, especially when the learning takes place in an online environment. Any malfunctioning software or hardware can bring an ongoing class to a standstill and interrupt the learning process. Similarly, if a student is not computer and tech savvy, his learning experience can be dissatisfactory. Though the learner feels there is no much cost, in reality there are some hidden costs like purchasing computer, installing secured internet connection, need web camera, printer etc. Thus, online learning is not fully free from cost. Often considered to be the lesser cousin of regular education, online education is often plagued by lack of enough good quality faculty members. In other cases, even if the instructor is good, he or she may not be comfortable with teaching in an online environment. Sometimes the technology might not do full justice to the delivery and design of the course. A student loses out in all these scenarios. Online education providers should realize that it is not the technology, but good and effective teachers that teach students

7. SWING IN INDIAN ONLINE EDUCATION

Online education in India has been on an upward swing in the last few years and the trend is expected to continue in the days to come maybe at a much accelerated pace. There is an ever-growing population of education-hungry students & professionals in India that is going

online. Because there are 50 crore students in India falling in the age bracket of 5 - 24 years and the country is just not equipped to provide a decent education to such a huge number only through the traditional mode. i.e classroom teaching. As per the statistics shared by COURSERA (world's largest open online education i.e. MOOC provider), there were 13 lakh online learners from India as compared to the total 180 lakh online learners on COURSERA. The Indian government aims to increase the enrollment (GER) in universities from 23.% in 2014-15 to 30% by the year 2030. But, practically this is not easy by just setting up more traditional classrooms & universities. (The Learning House, 2016)

8. CONCLUSION

In recent years, books are gradually getting replaced by electronic educational materials like optical discs or pen drives. Knowledge can also be shared via the Internet, which is accessible anywhere, anytime means helps to satisfy the hunger of learning. Thus, though the online education has a number of challenges ahead to reach majority in the world, slowly and steadily will gain popularity and it will be useful to huge number of people on the globe.

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Paper 11
**PERCEPTION AND EXPERIENCE OF USERS ON
MOOC'S SWAYAM - A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO
POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS' OF BELTHANGADY
TALUK**

Robin Joseph Sera¹ & Silvyn Shalita Lobo²

¹Lecturer in Commerce, Sacred Heart College, Madanthyar, Karnataka, India.

Email: robinsera361@gmail.com

Mobile: +91 99649 96649

²M.Com Final Year, Sacred Heart College, Madanthyar.

Email: srsilvynufs@gmail.com

Mobile: +91 94496 14827

Abstract:

Online learning uses technology for delivering the courses. Education with technology is considered as the most promising development in education. With technology globalization, the concept of learning and teaching has undergone a tremendous change. Technological usage in education provides a global learning environment, which allows accessing the course material anytime, anywhere, connect other learners, and get access to the content without considering any geographical boundaries. The significant changes in the use of technology in online education have seen the emergence of the concept of Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). SWAYAM platform is indigenously developed by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) and All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) with the help of Microsoft and would be ultimately capable of hosting 2000 courses and 80000 hours of learning: covering school, under-graduate, post-graduate, engineering, law and other professional courses. University Grants Commission (UGC) has vided Gazette Notification dated 19 th July 2016, notified Regulation, 2016 regarding 'Credit Framework for Online Learning Courses through SWAYAM'. SWAYAM has been developed under four-quadrant approaches: (1) video lecture, (2) specially prepared reading material that can be downloaded/printed (3) self-assessment tests through tests and quizzes and (4) an online discussion forum for clearing the doubts. SWAYAM is an indigenous IT Platform for hosting the Massive Open Online Courses. The study is conducted among the Postgraduate students of Belthangady taluk to know the experience of users and to know the various challenges faced by the students while accessing the various courses.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world is going digital, so should our learning. The phenomenal growth of ICT in the education system has had a tremendous impact globally. India has been quick enough to leverage technology for teaching learning processes as ICT has facilitated the accessibility to education

and promoting quality teaching and learning to learners of all age groups across the length and breadth of the country. Taking cognizance of such advancements, The Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India launched SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds), an indigenously developed platform aimed at providing learning opportunities to the learners through MOOCs (Massive Open Online Course) free of cost in a structured manner¹. The MOOCs on the SWAYAM are high quality, curriculum-based, interactive content in different subjects across disciplines of social sciences, arts, fine arts, humanities, natural & mathematical sciences, linguistics, languages, technology, management, teacher training and skill sector². These courses are developed by the best faculty of the country carefully chosen from various educational institutions across the country from Secondary till Post-Graduation level. The basic philosophy of MOOCs on SWAYAM is free learning for any one, anytime, Anywhere (AAA) with the facility of credit transfer for up to 20% of the courses in a programme. Although the programme is in the initial stage among Mangalore university affiliated colleges and there may be lot of problems and confusion among the student community and much more expectation towards the project so; the study is conducted in the Belthangady taluk in order to ascertain the experience of the post graduate students, who are already enrolled under MOOC's SWAYAM.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- ❖ To know the satisfaction level about SWAYAM course among the graduate students
- ❖ To find out the various problems faced while accessing the course.
- ❖ To know the expectations by the users regarding the Swayam platform.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kaveri et al. (2016), "The strength of SWAYAM lies in its qualitative evaluation systems as well as recognition of credits, equity of access and affordability. Traditional HEIs have a clear edge over global MOOCs and SWAYAM in terms of long term impact on citizen and society building and shaping individual opinions". Kanjlal (2016), "Mainstreaming the SWAYAM initiative with the formal education system will go a long way in realizing the dream of the nation in universal access of education. With appropriate planning and implementation, SWAYAM can play a pivotal role in Digital India and Skill India missions of the government of India". Bharti (2014), "SWAYAM is a platform for new India where quality education is affordable and self-learning is fruitful not only for enrolled but also for professionals and dropouts. With quality content, best online lectures, great discussions, knowledgeable assessment quizzes, SWAYAM will provide great opportunity to Indian students to learn without fearing from failure." P.K. Sahoo et al. (2018) "below average awareness of traditional, regular courses student towards MOOC's SWAYAM programme. Students are not self motivated to join SWAYAM programme. P Bhoopathi et al.(2018) SWAYAM mode distance education system. It has made the education easily accessible to anyone around the globe with the improved equity and quality in the education especially in Indian context.

4. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As per the New Higher Education policy, the Government is planning to render the education on the basis of equity, quality, and relevance and to promote the Life-Long Learning. The MHRD department has come up with the new platform called SWAYAM, although this Programme is in beginning stage, there is a lack of knowledge among the students' communities and academicians, on the same even though there are students who have already enrolled for the courses under SWAYAM website..

5. METHODOLOGY

The paper employed survey method to acquire the information regarding the students' experience with MOOC's SWAYAM. Target of the study is in Belthangady Taluk. The samples are students from different colleges. In online survey 43 students have responded for the study. Non Random Sampling method is used. To provide the theoretical background and strengthen the discussion books and the journals were referred. The collected data is presented in the form of tables.

6. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

The data is collected from the google forms and out of 43 respondents 34 are using the platform from last one month because the colleges are recently giving much importance towards the SWAYAM initiative. 7 respondents are using since one year and rest 02 respondents using from more than a year. This shows that students are came to know about the programme very recently and they are enrolled under the same. The source of awareness regarding the SWAYAM among the users, It is clear that 51% of the respondents are come to know about SWAYAM through their lecturers and 21% from the library staff and 19% respondents opines that through orientation they got the idea, here we can understand that the lecturers are encouraging the students towards the online courses. The various reasons to use SWAYAM platform by the respondents, 53% respondents opine that there is availability of large number of courses so the students can opt any of the interested courses without any regulations. 19% respondents are opines that it facilitates any time learning without the four wall and chalk and talk system. 12% feels that the platform have experienced faculty and 14% says the course method is good. Only 40% Respondents College is in the SWAYAM Local Chapter list that means they get all the information in a up to date manner. Remaining 60% of the respondent's college is not in the SWAYAM local chapter list. Duration of time spent for a particular course by the users, 68% respondents were weekly go through the topics and submits the assignments where as 19% of the respondents are access the once in a two days and only 12% of the students are daily go through the course and read related topics. Respondents face various problems while accessing the SWAYAM platform through App or Website. 40% of the respondents states that there is a difficult interface and it is difficult to surf the various courses. 26% of the respondents face the problem of breakdowns of website and app. 20% of the respondents face connectivity issues and rest 14% of the respondents face the problem of registration/login. With regard to the satisfaction level of users , it is clear that 72% of the respondents are satisfied with interface and courses offered by the SWAYAM website, whereas 28% of the respondents are not satisfied with the platform and the various reasons for the dissatisfaction, out of 12 dissatisfied respondents 5 respondents opines that they have to pay high charges for the certificate and it is not affordable

in the rural area colleges. 3 respondents says that they have to travel long distance to write the exams and rest of the respondents gives the reasons of low connectivity and confusions over the course. The various expectations by the users regarding the Swayam. 49% of the respondents believes that there is a need of more orientation regarding the same, 30% respondents expect the lower charges for the examination and certificate. 12% and 9% of the respondents opines that the website should use easy interface and it should conduct the web based examinations.

7. SUGGESSTIONS

The respective departments of MHRD and educational institutions need to provide more orientation to the student community and also should advertise the course in the social and print media. The website and app of SWAYAM should be redesign in such a manner that the users may not find any difficulties while surfing the courses and other course related information. The examination charge should be kept nominal, so that the students from rural colleges can afford and also the colleges should enroll themselves in the local chapters, so that they can apply for the fee waiving facility.

8. CONCLUSION

The MOOCs are the future of today's distance learning. They have made the education easily accessible to anyone anywhere anytime around the globe and made people's life more improved by providing flexible and quality learning as it was earlier. They have made a difference by providing free courses and enabled people and students' world around to participate, interact, discuss and learn from the renowned faculty of this world thereby improving people's live and bring out real change to communities as a whole. As per the UGC guidelines the colleges now started to encourage the students towards the online courses, though the students are aware about the platform still there are various technical problems that creates difficulties to the users so the respected stakeholder need to improve the quality and interface of the SWAYAM platform.

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Paper 12

PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AMONG SPOUSES OF MALE AT RISK DRINKERS-A STUDY

Sushma Soans¹

¹Assistant Professor, Dr. M. V. Shetty College of Social Work, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
Email: sushmasoans5@gmail.com

Abstract:

The consequences of alcoholism on the mental health of spouses of lifetime at risk drinkers are only known from the studies on alcoholics. The effects of alcoholism on a relationship or marriage are huge strain on the relationship. A study was conducted in a community of Mangalore. The researcher have been used interview schedule for collecting information on the objective of understanding personal profile, causes and problems .These spouses were less likely to be homemakers. Women often suffer cruel physical and emotional abuse from their alcoholic husbands. Even when he is not overtly abusive he's often disgusting in the way he talks and behaves when he's drunk. The spouses of alcoholics are usually so relieved when treatment is successful that they often think their marital troubles are over. Its true addiction makes it impossible to resolve marital conflicts. Descriptive research design has been used for the study by taking 50 samples. The study found that 60 per cent of the female spouses of alcoholics have been adjusted and also they try to keep themselves busy, socio economic conditions of them are poor.

Keywords: Alcoholism, Addiction, Relationship, Abuse, Stress, Treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem of alcoholism until a few decades ago was considered a moral; problem and a sign of social irresponsibility[1]. Alcoholism is one among the major social problem that our nation faces and it is a major block to the development of rural as well as urban areas. It is harmful not only for the individual but also for his family and the society at large. The emotional response to addictive illness in family members... frequently have their roots in guilt feelings. Grief is an emotional responds of his wife to addiction. For family members, grief is the result of all sorts of losses. Loss of prestige, loss of family and personal dignity, loss of feeling of love, loss of care and understanding, loss of security, loss of friends, loss of finance, loss of each and every areas of their life. According to Keller and Efron(1955), Alcoholism is characterized by the repeated drinking of alcoholic beverages to an extent that exceeds customary use or compliance with the social customs of the community and that adversely affects the drinkers health or interferes with his social or economic functioning. Addiction is the problem which affects not only the individual but the family and society also.

2. ALCOHOL AS A CAUSE OF FAMILY PROBLEM

It has always been known that problematic drinkers cause problems not only to themselves but also to their spouse, children, parents and their family members [8]. The impact of problematic drinking on the family is especially on the adolescents.

(i) **Roles:** Problematic drinking can change the roles played by family members in relation to one another and the outside world, the drinker might cease to perform his previous functions as a breadwinner or in relation to the support and supervision of children household chores or recreational activities [2].

(ii) **Routines:** The addicts behavior is likely to become unpredictable and disruptive imparting the family's capacity to plan activities in advance or to stick to familiar routines

(iii) **Rituals:** Family gathering such as Christmas or birthday, designed to celebrate and integrate the family, may be particularly subject to disruption either because of the absence of the drinker or perhaps much worsen their presence [8]

(iv) **Finance:** Money spent on alcohol is not available for other purpose. An alcohol problem may impair or destroy the drinker's capacity to earn a livelihood. Reducing earnings or unemployment are not infrequent consequences of drinking problem and these naturally affect the other members of the family and can have all sorts of repercussions [5]

3. IMPACT OF THE ALCOHOLISM IN THE FAMILY

(i) **Social Impact :** Interpersonal relationships are poor with neighbors and relatives due to the alcohol dependents behavior. They would be constant fights and arguments in the family and neighborhood [4]

(ii) **Financial Impact :** Absenteeism or ill health leading to lose of income[5]. Loans debts from various people.

(iii) **Values & Moral Standards:** Values in the family are very poor. Lying, stealing and fights are common [4]

(iv) **Cultural Areas:** Festivals, customs, rituals, tradition are all forgotten. Spouse may not have money or interest or due to ill health, may not be able to celebrate a festival.

(v) **Spouse or Partner Stress:** Alcoholism has a transforming effect on the spouse or partner that can create significant mental trauma and physical health problems. Divorce rates among couples where one or both partner's drinks are much higher than average [3]. As alcohol abuse or addiction progresses, the non-drinking spouse often grows into a compulsive care-taking role, which creates feelings of resentment, self-pity and exhaustion [4]

(vi) **Marital Sufferings:** Poor spousal communication [6], Increased anger and distress [6], Reduced intimacy and sexual desire, Increased marital abuse, Depleting finances spent on alcohol, The relationship between an alcohol abuser and his or her family is complex [7]. 'Family members report experiencing guilt, shame, anger, fear, grief and isolation due to the presence of an alcohol abuser in the family [10]. They are often subjected when they confront the drinking behavior of their alcohol abusing family members. Spouses in families where there is chronic excessive use of alcohol are frequently separated.

(vii) **Effects of Alcoholism on Families:** Treating alcoholic families is difficult and complex. Often treatment is not entirely successful for family members, even when the alcohol abuse or addict eventually reforms [9]. The effects of alcoholism in families are difficult to overcome; yet

without treatment, they can be devastating for the long-term. With the right approach and support, positive steps can be taken to improve lives [7]. Healthcare professionals may recommend a multi-faceted treatment approach that includes group family therapy, as well as individualized treatment for each family member [8] .

4. TREATMENT METHODS

The treatment may take the form of one or more of the following pedagogies. The intervention based on the result of this study indicates that greater psychological distress among these wives was most strongly associated with lower satisfaction with the marital relationship, presence of domestic violence, lower perceived social support from family [5]. The key treatment methods include Out-Patient Programs, In-Patient Programs, Peer Support Groups, Psycho-Social Therapy and Medication-Assisted Treatment.

5. CONCLUSION

By concluding it can be said that alcoholism is a family disease and the spouse of an alcoholic is the most affected person in the family. Alcohol is a weakness of character. The moralist looks at it as a vice, law finds the consequential act of alcoholism as a crime, the clergyman considers it as a sin, a psychiatric professional recognizes it as a disease, which can be treated. It is not only harmful to the individual but also families. If timely help is not provided to such families, they may become a problem to the society.

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

SAMAGRA GNANA

UNDERGRADUATE

B.Des. UX (User Experience)
B.Des. Fashion Design
B.Tech Computer Science & Engg.
B.Tech Mechanical Engineering
B.Tech Civil Engineering
B.Tech Electronics & Comm. Engg.
B.Tech Cloud Tech. & Info. Security
B.Tech Data Science
B.Tech Nanotechnology
BPT Physiotherapy
B.Sc. Cardio Vascular Technology
B.Sc. Perfusion Technology
B.Sc. Medical Lab Technology
B.Sc. Renal Dialysis Technology
B.Sc. Optometry
B.Sc. OT & Anaesthesia Technology
B.Sc. Imaging Technology
B.Sc. Respiratory Care Technology
B.Sc. Forensic Science
B.Sc. Digital Film Making & VFX
B.Sc. Animation & VFX
B.Sc. Interior Design
B.Sc. Fashion Technology
B.Sc. Hotel Management
BHMCT HM & Catering Technology
BCA Software Development
BCA Cloud Tech. & Info. Security
BCA Info. Security & Mobile Apps.
BCA Network & Server Admin.
BBA (Honors)
BBA Aviation Management
BBA Aviation & Airport Mgmt.
BBA Port Management
BBA Logistics & Supply Chain Mgmt.
BBA International Business
BBA Financial Services
BBA Journalism & Mass Comm.
BHA Hospital Administration
B.Com (Honors)
B.Com Int. Accounting with ACCA
B.A. Journalism & Mass Comm.
B.Ed. Education

POSTGRADUATE

M.Des. UX (User Experience)
M.Tech. Structural Engineering
M.Tech. Nanotechnology
M.Tech. Computer Science
M.Tech. Research Based (All Branches)
M.S. Research Based (All Branches)
M.Sc. MLT Clinical Biochemistry
M.Sc. MLT Haem. & Blood Transfusion
M.Sc. MLT Microbiology & Immunology
M.Sc. Echocardiography
M.Sc. Cardiac Catheterisation & Interv.
M.Sc. Respiratory Care Technology
M.Sc. Medical Imaging Technology
M.Sc. Anesthesia and OT Technology
M.Sc. Psychology & Counselling
MPT Physiotherapy
MBA Dual Specialization
Finance & Marketing
Marketing & HRM
Finance & HRM
MBA Super Speciality
Aviation Management
Port Management
Business Analytics
Logistics & SCM
Hotel Management & Tourism
Hospital & Health Care Management
M.Com. Finance & Banking
M.Com. Auditing & Taxation
M.Com. With Integrated ACCA
MCA Lateral Entry & Dual Specialization
DS & Cloud Computing
MSW Master of Social Work
Dual Specialization

RESEARCH

M.Phil. | Ph.D. | D.Sc. | D.Litt.
Science, Commerce, Economics,
Management, Social Sciences, Humanities,
Engineering & Technology, Education,
Inter-Disciplinary, Health Sciences

CONTACT US

Administrative Office
G.H.S Road,
Mangaluru- 575 001
Karnataka, India.

T 0824-2412382, 2444891, 2422381
M 9741141433, 9980951074
E admission@srinivasuniversity.edu.in
W www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in